

EVORoads

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE AND ON-THE-EDGE SAFETY TOOLS V1

Project deliverable D2.2

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIRHD	Artificial Intelligence Road Hazard Detection
CA	Cracking Area
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CVAT	Computer Vision Annotation Tool
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DoF	Deep of focus
DRD	Danish Road Directorate
GM	Green Mobility
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Models
HAIM	Hazard aware infrastructure monitoring
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IR	Infrared Laser
IRI	International Roughness Index
JNO	Jetson Nano Orin
KP	Knapsack Problem
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MPD	Mean Profile Depth
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
PCI	Pavement Condition Index
SED	Straight Edge Deviation
TLS	Transport Layer Security

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UAV	An Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WD	Wire Deviation
WP	Work Package
YOLO	You only Look Once – Computer Vision Tool

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Project executive summary

The EC-funded EvoRoads (Evolutionary Solutions for Realising a Holistic Safe System Approach for All Road Users) is committed to advancing the European Union's Vision Zero initiative by implementing a comprehensive framework that integrates innovative models, tools, and services for data-driven safety assessments.

The project involves the development of a connectivity platform that digitalizes transport infrastructure assets and ensures the seamless integration of safety assessment services. By leveraging advanced artificial intelligence, EvoRoads analyses infrastructure monitoring data at various geospatial levels, enabling proactive risk warnings and supporting road operators in managing maintenance more effectively, which enhances both safety and operational efficiency. It also defines safety criteria and quantification methods for key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor safety performance as part of the "Safe System" approach.

The results are developed alongside 5 axes: (1) an Evolutionary Safety Assessment Framework setting the basis by defining how to measure road safety in a multilayered catalogue; (2) a Road Asset & Safety Management Digital Twin collecting and distributing safety data; (3) Advanced Monitoring Safety Systems using that data that enable infrastructure owners to obtain clear insights on their roads' level of safety; (4) Proactive Safety Warning Systems ensuring that critical safety issues are raised pro-actively and in real-time to prevent safety hazards; and finally, all these results are combined in (5) Solutions Integration, Augmentation and Impact Assessment tools and products allowing for take-up of the results in the wider market. These axes converge into a Safe Mobility Data Space where all data related to EvoRoads' safety criteria and solutions are combined.

EvoRoads' methodologies and technologies will be validated in four Living Labs (LLs) addressing diverse road user scenarios across urban and rural environments to ensure broad applicability and effectiveness. EvoRoads LLs are situated in Spain (focusing on Hazard-aware assets for better infrastructure safety level for existing and future roads users), Italy (focusing on Dynamic Road infrastructure safety diagnosis enhanced by emerging vehicle and digital technologies), Latvia (focusing on Automated (advanced) low-cost infrastructure monitoring and diagnostics: road hot spots, bridges, tunnels), and Romania (focusing on Remote sensing and warning technologies for better infrastructure and road conditions).

The EvoRoads project runs from May 2024 until April 2027. A scale-up event is foreseen towards the end of the project to allow for the wider market to consider EvoRoads' results and to help provide ways forward.

Social Media link:

For further information please visit evoroads-project.eu

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Deliverable executive summary

This deliverable, D2.2 – Predictive Maintenance and On-the-Edge Safety Tools V1, presents the progress achieved within Work Package 2 (WP2) of the EvoRoads project, which focuses on the development of advanced infrastructure monitoring systems and predictive maintenance strategies. The document specifically covers the results of T2.3 and T2.4, which address two complementary components: the development of a predictive maintenance framework and the deployment of on-the-edge sensing and Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based road safety tools.

T2.3 focuses on designing a predictive maintenance system that integrates data from traditional inspection methods with real-time inputs from new sensing technologies. The system includes three core components: a prognostics module that forecasts the evolution of road conditions, an optimisation module that recommends cost-effective maintenance interventions based on multiple objectives (e.g., safety, cost, environmental impact), and a post-repair analysis module that incorporates feedback from completed repairs to improve future decision-making. These components are tightly integrated into a unified maintenance planning framework that is adaptable to different road segments and infrastructure conditions.

Task T2.4 involves the design, development, and first functional integration of two tools that operate on-the-edge to improve road monitoring capabilities. The first tool, HAIM (Hazard-Aware Infrastructure Monitoring), is a physical device equipped with a combination of sensors including LiDAR, infrared thermometers, ultrasonic rangefinders, GPS, and magnetometers. It is designed for deployment in rural or low-infrastructure environments and provides continuous monitoring of road surface conditions, environmental variables, and vehicle activity. The second tool, AIRHD (Artificial Intelligence for Road Hazard Detection), is a software solution based on deep learning and computer vision. It processes video streams from existing surveillance cameras to detect road hazards such as vehicles, animals, debris, and poor weather conditions, providing real-time alerts and data for infrastructure managers.

The combination of these systems represents a significant step forward in enabling intelligent, automated, and proactive management of road safety and maintenance. Both solutions are designed to function independently or in coordination, allowing for flexible deployment strategies depending on the monitoring context and infrastructure availability.

The main conclusion of this deliverable is that the core architecture of both the predictive maintenance framework and the edge-based monitoring systems has been successfully implemented and validated at the prototype level. This includes the completion of key software modules, initial hardware integration, and early-stage field validation. The tools developed provide a solid foundation for further testing in pilot environments, where their combined use will allow for the demonstration of a data-driven, real-time, and cost-effective approach to infrastructure maintenance and hazard prevention.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive overview of the first integrated release of these tools, document their technical specifications, and establish their readiness for subsequent phases of integration, validation, and demonstration within the EvoRoads project's Living Labs.

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1 Introduction

The following document summarises the work carried out under T2.3 and T2.4, both belonging to (WP2) “Advanced infrastructure monitoring and predictive-maintenance tools.” Task T2.3 centres on the design of a predictive-maintenance framework that merges legacy inspection data with real-time inputs from novel sensing technologies. By synthesising horizontal- and vertical-infrastructure information generated by the AI system of T2.2, the framework applies predictive analytics and multi-objective optimisation to schedule maintenance interventions that balance cost, ride quality, environmental impact and road-user safety. The process begins with comprehensive data acquisition across the road network, continues with optimised intervention planning for each segment, and closes the loop with post-repair impact analysis to refine future decisions.

Task T2.4, in turn, delivers the first release of an on-the-edge device that measures road conditions, detects vehicles and debris, and assesses asphalt quality through computer-vision algorithms and dedicated sensors. While the device’s core sensing suite (temperature, ultrasonic ranging and LiDAR surface scanning) will be integrated in the final hardware, its vision module has been decoupled to exploit the existing security-camera infrastructure at the living lab in Tarragona, Spain. Custom AI models run on these cameras to perform object-detection tasks in real time.

1.1 Mapping EvoRoads outputs

Purpose of this section is to map EvoRoads Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1 Adherence to EvoRoads GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

EVORoads GA COMPONENT TITLE	EVORoads GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
DELIVERABLE			
D2.2 Predictive Maintenance and on-the-edge safety tools V1	The first release of the predictive maintenance diagnosis and prognosis tool together with the on-the-edge platform of sensory and communication technologies.	Chapter 3 and Chapter 4	Chapters 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 4.1, and 4.2 address Tasks 2.3 and 2.4 in a structured manner, covering the requirements of the GA Deliverable. The sections first present the development of the on-the-edge platform integrating sensing and communication technologies (T2.3), followed by the initial release of the predictive maintenance diagnosis and prognosis tool (T2.4).
TASKS			
T2.3 Predictive maintenance and post-		Chapter 3	This section corresponds to the AI models for detecting cracks and road

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impact repair analysis solutions

imperfections to see how road data is analysed.

T2.4 On-the-edge and connected road safety systems		Chapter 4	Section 4.2 details the physical monitoring device, and Section 4.3 focuses on the software component powered by artificial intelligence.
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1.2 Deliverable overview and report structure

This deliverable describes the work carried out in Tasks T2.3 and T2.4 of WP2, which focuses on advanced road infrastructure monitoring and predictive maintenance tools. The report is divided into several chapters, each addressing a specific part of the work.

- **Chapter 1** This section explains the organisation of the document, the changes made, and its development.
- **Chapter 2** explains how the project aligns with the European AI Act and the steps taken to ensure compliance.
- **Chapter 3** covers Task 2.3. It describes the development of a predictive maintenance system, including:
 - How future road conditions are predicted (Section 3.2),
 - How resources are planned and optimised for maintenance (Section 3.3),
 - And how the system analyses the results of repairs to improve future decisions (Section 3.4).
- **Chapter 4** presents the results of Task 2.4. This includes:
 - The design and construction of the HAIM device, which monitors road conditions using sensors (Section 4.2),
 - And the AIRHD software, which uses artificial intelligence to detect hazards from camera video (Section 4.3).
- **Chapter 5** This section explains where the technology developed by the company IDIADA will be tested
- **Chapter 6** This section describes how the technology developed in Chapter 4 will be validated using standardised templates based on predefined KPIs. The validation will follow a structured framework aligned with key performance indicators, and an example of KPI application is included to illustrate the assessment process.
- **Chapter 7** This chapter presents the scientific contribution of the technology developed in Chapters 3 and 4, highlighting its relevance within the broader research and innovation context.
- **Chapter 8** This chapter presents a summary and concluding remarks on the technological developments described throughout Chapters 3 and 4.

Each chapter focuses on practical developments and their application, following the objectives defined in the project's Grant Agreement.

1.3 Progress since the first deliverable version

Since the release of the first version of this deliverable, the document has undergone a structural revision to improve clarity, coherence, and alignment with the updated template. In addition, contributions from multiple project partners have been actively integrated, particularly in relation to Task 2.3, which is now fully incorporated in this version.

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Each partner is requested to fill in the table below to describe their expected contributions, relevant expertise, and tools/methods they plan to apply for Task 2.3. The partners involved in Task 2.3 have reported the following progress:

Table 2. Partner contribution description table for Task 2.3

Partner	Expected Contributions to Task 2.3	Expertise / Tools / Methods
DTU (12PM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designing predictive maintenance system - Prognostic Predictive Module - Optimisation Modules - Asset Management Plan - Post Repair Analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building an integrated framework that combines pavement condition monitoring, risk estimation, and optimisation-driven decision support. - Estimating the likelihood through machine learning model that each road segment (in rural/highway area...) will require intervention. It uses pavement condition metrics from sensor-derived data to assess degradation. - Density based clustering methods for high-risk segments and providing probabilistic maintenance risks and cost estimation for each group. - An integer programming model is used to prioritise the interventions where they will have the highest impact. - Developing visualisation interface that provides exact GPS hotspots for maintenance location.
INLE (4PM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Road Risk Identification and Intervention Support Tool - AI Functionalities for Multi-Level Decision Support - Risk-Based Use Case Scenarios for Strategic and Operational Planning - Tool Integration and Enhancement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk profiling for targeted safety interventions in road networks - Clustering and trend estimation using Gaussian Mixture Models and least squares linear fit estimation - Assessment of three distinct types of risk: (i) overall accident risk, (ii) accident growth trend over time, and (iii) a combined score that balances both and design of corresponding functionalities - Use cases demonstrating multi-level decision support (municipality and regional) for identifying high-risk areas and guiding interventions
CEA (4PM)	Development of Vision-based AI tools dedicated detection and classification defect of traffic signs	-The under-development tool is relied on the Ultralytics YOLO11, pretrained model that we have fine-tuned on traffic sign datasets to specialise the model on the detection of traffic signs present in processed video (this work is done in collaboration with the task T 2.2 where we have collected traffic signs datasets and developed traffic sign detection tool. In task T2.3, we under developing models to classify the nature of traffic signs: damaged or not and type of damage. We will use real and synthetic data
UCY (3PM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spatial analysis of road surface damage leveraging AI-based crack and pothole detection - Development of clustering methods to identify concentrated pavement damage areas - Integration of spatial proximity metrics to support predictive maintenance decision-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deep learning (YOLOv11 model) for defect detection - UAV imagery processing, geospatial defect mapping - Clustering methods combined with spatial analysis for identifying damage patterns - Support for integration of distance-based indicators into PMS and predictive analytics modules

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- Contribution to a Distance-Based Pavement Condition Index (DBPCI)

EUT (2PM)	Generation of synthetic data for training algorithms	We will modify image data provided by DTU to add information about the potholes.
IDIADA (2PM)	-Santa Oliva Pilot owner supporting tools to be implemented in the pilot	-Providing specifications, insights for maintenance from a test track owner point of view -Organising the Santa Oliva pilot (device installation and maintenance, hosting the EvoRoads partners, performing necessary tests for data collection)
BEIA (2PM)	Pothole Detection Using Drones	Key Steps: -Data Collection – drones with high-resolution cameras -Image Preprocessing - using OpenCV -Model Training - deep learning model based on the YOLO v8 architecture -Detection Pipeline -Geotagging and Reporting - based on drone GPS metadata integrated with GIS platforms -Deployment & Optimisation - on edge devices (e.g., Jetso Nano)
LINKS (1PM)	- Contribution in integration with the Digital Twin - Contribution in integration with Italian Pilot	- Development of Digital Twin and DT-based applications - Pilot Site leader

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2 AI Act Compliance in the EvoRoads project

To guarantee the responsible development and use of AI, the European Union has defined the concept of Trustworthy AI based on three fundamental pillars: compliance with existing laws and regulations (Lawful), adherence to fundamental human values (Ethical) and technical security and resilience against risks (Robust). As outlined in the [Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI](#), these principles have been translated into practical requirements, such as transparency, human oversight, data protection, and fairness.

The [AI Act](#) is a European regulation that integrates the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI into a binding regulatory framework, establishing concrete rules, classifying AI-based systems, and imposing stringent requirements for high-risk applications. The regulation introduces a risk-based classification system for AI-based systems, dividing them into four main categories:

- Unacceptable risk: Prohibited systems, such as those employing subliminal manipulative techniques or social scoring.
- High risk: Applications impacting critical sectors (e.g., healthcare, infrastructure, mobility) that are subject to strict compliance requirements.
- Limited risk: Systems that require transparency obligations, such as chatbots or deepfakes.
- Minimal risk: Unregulated systems, such as spam filters or AI-powered video games.

The AI Act seeks to balance technological innovation with the protection of fundamental rights, promoting the responsible use of AI. It includes human oversight, data security, and non-discrimination provisions while supporting AI-based research and development in strategic sectors.

EvoRoads Project is committed to fully complying with the EU AI Act, its core principles, and the Trustworthy AI criteria, ensuring that all developed AI-based technologies are lawful, ethical, robust, and respectful of human rights and values.

The EvoRoads project involves multiple entities, meaning any subject (company, individual, or public body) engaged in developing, distributing, or using an AI-based system. Depending on their role, each entity has specific obligations and responsibilities to ensure compliance with European AI regulations. The key entities involved in the EvoRoads Project include:

- Provider: A company, public entity, or individual that develops an AI-based system or a general-purpose AI model and places it on the market or into service under its own name or brand.
- Deployer: Any entity using an AI system under its authority (e.g., companies, public bodies), except for personal, non-professional use.

To correctly classify the role of each EvoRoads beneficiary and the characteristics of the AI-based systems being developed, used, or distributed, the project will leverage the [EU AI Act Compliance Checker](#).

By answering a series of questions, this tool will support EvoRoads beneficiaries in identifying the risk level of EvoRoads AI-based system and being informed about specific articles of the AI Act to be considered to ensure full compliance with trustworthy AI principles. The results provided by the tool will be documented in project deliverables dedicated to the EvoRoads AI-based solutions.

By leveraging the EU AI Act Compliance Checker, the EvoRoads project will ensure full compliance with European AI regulations, fostering the development and adoption of safe, ethical, and reliable AI-based systems in road transport.

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3 Predictive maintenance and post-impact repair analysis solutions

3.1 Overview

Maintaining the availability, safety, and peak performance of road networks is a key priority for infrastructure authorities tasked with preserving road systems. To address this challenge, developing a predictive maintenance framework that synthesises diverse data inputs and leverages advanced algorithms for strategic planning is crucial. Within the EvoRoads initiative, Task T2.3 focuses on designing this framework by integrating predictive analytics, multi-objective optimisation methods, and data-driven strategies to enhance road maintenance scheduling and decision-making processes.

Figure 1. The overview of predictive road maintenance infrastructure

The proposed system leverages the information about the road's horizontal and vertical infrastructure, which is provided by the AI-based system developed in Task 2.2. However, since this data is currently unavailable, Task 2.3 has temporarily adapted by using external datasets from similar road environments to train and validate the predictive maintenance models. This ensures continuity in development while preserving compatibility with the data pipeline anticipated from Task 2.2. This predictive maintenance system is designed to prioritise maintenance interventions by analysing various parameters, including road conditions, maintenance costs, ride quality, environmental impact, and safety. It also accounts for legacy data from road inspection systems in combination with real-time data from novel inspection technologies.

The process starts with gathering information from the road network, as depicted in the diagram, followed by the generation of a maintenance plan that addresses the specific needs of each road segment. The maintenance decisions are made based on a set of assumptions and constraints that guide the Optimisation process, ensuring that the road network remains in optimal condition while balancing costs and resources considerations. The system is also designed to evaluate the efficacy of maintenance actions through post-impact repair analysis, providing a feedback loop that continuously improves future maintenance decisions.

3.2 Prognostics and optimisation system design

3.2.1 Prediction module

The prediction module forms the foundation of the predictive maintenance system. It integrates data from both legacy road inspection systems and novel inspection technologies introduced in Task 2.2. The module is designed to estimate the likelihood of future maintenance needs across road segments by learning patterns of infrastructure degradation. By using advanced machine learning and prognostics algorithms, the model is designed to support crossroad generalisation, which can be trained on one road (e.g., an urban route) and used to predict maintenance needs on another with similar characteristics. This enables scalable deployment across road networks even when direct data is limited, while ensuring

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that predictive accuracy is preserved through consistent data representation and road context. To provide a comprehensive analysis, the prognostics module performs the following functions:

Data Sources: The accuracy and reliability of the *Prognostics Module* in predicting road infrastructure degradation heavily relies on the quality and diversity of data inputs. To ensure that the model can effectively forecast the condition of road networks, a range of data sources are integrated into the system. Theoretically, these data sources should be multi-dimensional and include sensor data, image data, traffic and environmental data, and historical maintenance records. Each of these datasets contributes unique information that enhances the model's ability to generate accurate and actionable predictions. Currently, we do not have all the necessary available data sources of the EvoRoads pilot sites that could contribute all those types of datasets simultaneously, so we just focus on the sensor data for the prognostic module. Once all data types become available for the same pilot, we plan to merge all models into a *multi-modal model* that can analyse all types of data together, especially for raw data and image data.

- Vibration Data:** This data comes from road vibration sensors placed along road segments. It captures the vibrations caused by vehicles moving over distressed road surfaces, enabling anomaly detection related to road degradation. The vibration data used in this project is sourced from the [Lira Project](#), specifically for the *Copenhagen area in Denmark*. While Denmark is not one of the official EvoRoads pilot countries, this dataset was selected due to its high quality, availability, and compatibility with our predictive modelling requirements. It serves as a robust starting point for algorithm development and benchmarking, enabling us to pre-train and validate models prior to their application to pilot-specific data from other countries such as Spain or Italy. The dataset integrates data from more than 50 in-vehicle sensor signals acquired from Renault Zoe electric cars operated by Green Mobility (GM) with 92 road condition parameters collected by standard vehicles operated by the Danish Road Directorate (DRD). It is important to note that the raw data in LiRA-CD is unaligned and unstructured. Therefore, several pre-processing steps are recommended prior to analysis such as re-orientation, map-matching, interpolation or data structuring.

Figure 2. The overview of data infrastructure from LIRA project

Infrastructure Condition Prediction: The Infrastructure Condition Prediction module aims to estimate the probability that a road segment will require maintenance based on sensor-derived pavement condition metrics. These include the important parameters such as *International Roughness Index (IRI)*, *Mean Profile Depth (MPD)*, *Straight Edge Deviation (SED)*, *Wire Deviation (WD)*, and *Cracking Area (CA)*. Each road segment $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is represented as a feature vector combining these metrics, where d is the number of features. In the absence of ground truth labels, the threshold-based maintenance flag $M(X_i) \in \{0,1\}$, defined from pavement condition metrics, serves as a weak supervision signal for model training. This flag captures whether a road segment exceeds anomaly-informed condition thresholds and thus requires maintenance. It predicts the future state of the infrastructure, identifying potential failure points before they occur.

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To support scalable deployment, the model is designed to generalise a crossroads of similar type. Let Ω_{train} and Ω_{test} be datasets from two roads R_{train} and R_{test} respectively (e.g., both urban).

Figure 3. The map of 2 highway routes (M3 and M13) and 2 urban routes (CPH1 and CPH6) surrounds the Copenhagen area with their distances

The model is trained on Ω_{train} : $f = Train(\Omega_{train})$. Let the predicted condition of road segment x_i^{test} in Ω_{test} i at time t be denoted as $p_i^{test}(t)$. The evolution of this condition on Ω_{test} , assuming similar feature distributions:

$$p_i^{test}(t) = f(x_i^{test}(t)), \forall x_i^{test}(t) \in \Omega_{test}.$$

This prediction strategy enables the use of one road to predict maintenance needs on another, provided they share structural and operational characteristics (e.g., urban layout, traffic profile, sensor data format). The performance of the classification model is evaluated using standard metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1 Score. These metrics are derived from the counts of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN).

Figure 4. Left: The Confusion matrix of classification model with 2562 training data points in urban road CPH1 and 2295 testing data points in urban road CPH6. Right: The ROC curve from classification model with AUC = 0.96

Road Segmentation Evaluation: The road network is segmented $x_i^{test}(t)$ based on the predicted condition $p_i^{test}(t)$, allowing for targeted maintenance interventions:

- $x_i^{test}(t)$ is good if $p_i^{test}(t) < P_{min}$
- $x_i^{test}(t)$ is moderate if $P_{min} \leq p_i^{test}(t) < P_{threshold}$
- $x_i^{test}(t)$ is bad if $P_{threshold} \leq p_i^{test}(t)$

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Where $P_{threshold}$ and P_{min} are predefined condition thresholds. For example, the following table presents the classification performance of the maintenance prediction model on the CPH6 urban road and the M13 highway road, using a decision threshold of 0.2. The model demonstrates strong generalisation across both environments, achieving high accuracy of 98.2% on CPH6 and 97.19% on M13. Notably, the model attains perfect recall (100%) on the CPH6 dataset, indicating that it successfully identified all actual maintenance needs in the urban scenario. This is complemented by a precision of 74.29%, resulting in an overall F1 score of 85.25%. On the M13 highway, the model maintains robust performance with an 83.05% recall and 60.49% precision, yielding an F1 score of 70.00%. While performance slightly drops in the highway context - likely due to variations in road segment characteristics or traffic dynamics - the results still reflect a reliable balance between sensitivity and false alarms. These findings suggest that the model is effective in diverse operational settings and can be adapted to both urban and highway maintenance planning.

Table 3 The Performance Metrics for Maintenance Prediction on testing data (Threshold = 0.2)

METRIC	CPH6 URBAN (%)	M13HIGHWAY (%)
Accuracy	98.2	97.19
Precision	74.29	60.49
Recall	100.00	83.05
F1 Score	85.25	70.00

Risk Estimation:

The Random Forest model is used to generate the probability score for risk estimation. This technique is well-suited for handling complex, high-dimensional data and can model non-linear relationships between the input features and the **target risk score**. The overall risk for each road segment i is expressed as:

$$R_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T f_t(X_i)$$

Where:

- R_i is the probability of failure for road segment i ,
- T is the number of decision trees in the Random Forest,
- $f_t(X_i)$ is the output of the t - th decision tree for input features X_i .

The output probability score is a value between 0 and 1, where values closer to 1 indicate higher risk, and values closer to 0 indicate lower risk. As a key outcome of the Optimisation workflow, we develop a set of **maintenance map** of road segments identified as high-risk based on predicted degradation probabilities. Each place icon is characterised by its geographic extent, risk score, and estimated intervention cost. The cost model integrates:

- Labour cost estimated from predicted repair time,
- Material cost estimated from pavement condition variables,
- Transportation cost is estimated from segment lengths.
- This cost-driven prioritisation ensures efficient and feasible allocation of available maintenance resources

Overall, this **visual representation** supports operational planning by clearly showing priority zones, enabling authorities to align resources and scheduling with areas of greatest urgency.

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Figure 5. A dynamic GPS map for visualising the maintenance places from random forest model with provided information such as the location, the maintenance probability and the estimated costs except images

To aggregate individual risk scores into actionable groups, we apply the **DBSCAN** (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) algorithm. This unsupervised spatial clustering method groups road segments into clusters (i.e., maintenance hotspots) based on:

- Geographic proximity (latitude, longitude), and
- High maintenance probability ($R_i > \tau$ where τ is a threshold).

Let:

- $S = \{i \mid R_i > \tau\}$ be the set of high-risk segments.
- Each cluster C_k contains a subset of these segments.

For each cluster C_k , let denote n_k be the number of segments in cluster C_k . We compute the *group-level risk estimation* as the *average maintenance probability*:

$$p_k = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i \in C_k} R_i$$

Figure 6. Different scales of dynamic GPS map for visualisation of clustering maintenance hotspots on the M3 and M13 highway via DBSCAN ($\epsilon = 0.005$, minPts = 5).

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Clustering-based risk estimation offers several key advantages for predictive maintenance. Here are several benefits of our methods:

1. *Spatial Awareness*: Groups high-risk segments into coherent geographical clusters, making maintenance planning more intuitive and location focused.
2. *Noise Reduction*: Averages out individual prediction errors, resulting in more robust and reliable risk estimates.
3. *Prioritisation Support*: Helps identify maintenance hotspots where interventions will have the greatest impact.
4. *Efficiency*: Reduces the number of decision units, simplifying the Optimisation process for large networks.
5. *Integrated Planning*: Enables maintenance decisions to consider both risk and associated costs at the cluster level.

3.2.2 Optimisation module

Once the future conditions and risks are predicted, the Optimisation module is responsible for determining the most effective and efficient maintenance plan. This module employs a multi-objective Optimisation framework to balance various factors such as maintenance costs, resources constraints, environmental impact, and safety. The objective is to prioritise clusters of road segments where maintenance will deliver the highest infrastructure value within given resource constraints.

The Optimisation model considers the following objectives:

1. **Risk Reduction (Benefit Maximisation)**: Clusters are ranked based on their normalised average maintenance probability and the number of affected segments. This allows the system to prioritise zones where the aggregated likelihood of failure is highest.
2. **Ride Quality**: By targeting clusters with high IRI or low MPD values, the system seeks to maintain or restore acceptable ride quality, contributing to both user comfort and road durability.
3. **Environmental Impact**: The Optimisation model also takes into account the environmental impact of maintenance activities, striving to reduce carbon emissions and resource consumption where possible.
4. **Safety and Reliability**: Ensuring the safety of road users by minimising degradation risks and maintaining infrastructure reliability is a critical consideration in the Optimisation framework.

The output is an optimal set of maintenance clusters selected under a defined budget constraint. The model uses [integer programming](#) to ensure that selected clusters maximise overall benefit (risk reduction and quality) while staying within cost and capacity limits. This results in a maintenance plan that is data-driven, spatially coherent, and aligned with real-world planning needs.

Let $x_k \in \{0,1\}$ is a binary variable indicating whether cluster k is selected and N is the number of clusters.

Multi-Objective Criteria:

The Optimisation model evaluates clusters based on the following key objectives:

1. **Risk Reduction (Benefit Maximisation)**: Each cluster C_k has an estimated average maintenance probability p_k normalised to ρ_k . The **total benefit** of intervening in cluster is defined as $\rho_k \cdot n_k$ where n_k be the number of road segments in the cluster.

Resource Constraints: In real-world road infrastructure maintenance, decision-making is not only driven by technical needs or predicted risk but also by practical limitations on available resources. The resource constraint ensures that the Optimisation output is feasible in operational, financial, and logistical terms.

1. **Budget Constraint**: The most critical constraint in the Optimisation model is the **financial budget** available for maintenance interventions. Each cluster C_k has an estimated total cost B_k derived from distance, labour, materials, and transportation. The total cost of selected clusters must not exceed the total budget B :

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$$\sum_{k=1}^N C_k \cdot x_k \leq B$$

2. **Labour Availability:** Each maintenance cluster requires labour for inspection, preparation, and execution of repairs. Let L_k denote the required labour hours for cluster k . If the total labour capacity available in the planning period is L_{max} , the constraint is:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N L_k \cdot x_k \leq L_{max}$$

This constraint is particularly relevant for public agencies with fixed or seasonal staffing levels.

3. **Material Constraints:** Maintenance actions require specific materials (e.g., asphalt, concrete). Let M_k represent the volume of materials required for cluster k , and M_k the total material stock or delivery capacity:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N M_k \cdot x_k \leq M_{max}$$

This constraint helps avoid bottlenecks due to limited material availability, especially in remote or high-demand periods.

4. **Equipment and Crew Constraints:** Some interventions may require specialised equipment (e.g., milling machines) or multiple crews. Let E_k denote the number of crews or equipment units needed for cluster k , and E_{max} be the total available units:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N E_k \cdot x_k \leq E_{max}$$

This constraint reflects logistical capacity and helps in scheduling multi-site operations without overlap or delays.

5. **Policy and Geographic Constraints:** Some clusters may be restricted due to:

- *Permit limitations*, e.g., protected urban areas,
- *Seasonal regulations*, e.g., no maintenance during winter,
- *Priority zones*, e.g., school or hospital zones requiring faster repairs.

These constraints are typically modelled as: $x_k = 0$ if cluster k violates policy/geographic constraint. This allows the model to automatically exclude clusters that are infeasible to address during the planning horizon.

Optimisation Algorithm: A multi-objective Optimisation model has been implemented to select clusters under a fixed budget constraint. The model balances risk reduction (via normalised probability scores and segment counts) with estimated maintenance costs (including distance, labour, materials, and transport). An integer programming formulation is used to prioritise clusters for intervention in the Optimisation model:

$$\max \sum_{k=1}^N \rho_k \cdot n_k \cdot x_k$$

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$$\circ \left(\begin{array}{c} C_1 \ C_2 \ \dots \ C_N \\ L_1 \ L_2 \ \dots \ L_N \\ M_1 \ M_2 \ \dots \ M_N \\ E_1 \ E_2 \ \dots \ E_N \end{array} \right)_{4 \times N} \cdot (x_1 \ x_2 \ \dots \ x_N)^T \leq (B \ L_{max} \ M_{max} \ E_{max})^T$$

$\circ \ x_k = 0$ for excluded cluster

This formulation is equivalent to a **knapsack problem (KP)**, where the goal is to select the most valuable combination of items (clusters) without exceeding the capacity (budget).

Maintenance Scheduling: The solution in the integer programming process typically runs efficiently even for networks with hundreds of clusters via solvers such as **CPLEX** or **GUROBI**. Once the prioritised clusters are identified, a scheduling plan is generated based on the availability of resources (personnel, equipment, materials). The scheduling model considers spatial continuity to reduce transportation costs and idle times. It ensures that no two geographically close interventions are planned simultaneously if resource sharing is necessary. Because of lacking the necessary data, we could not count the constraints from labour availability, material constraints, equipment and crew constraints, and policy and geographic constraints for the implements of integer programming.

Optimization Results (Cluster Level):

Cluster	Cluster_Euclidean	total_cost	avg_probability	num_segments	Scheduled
0	0	1400.000000	0.444286	7	1.0
1	1	3600.000000	0.225556	18	1.0
2	2	6184.889088	0.444545	11	1.0
3	3	79960.015766	0.338000	10	1.0
4	4	65985.760247	0.271429	7	0.0

Figure 7. Cluster Maintenance Summary for M13 highway in scheduling under provided budget 100000 euros

Given an available maintenance budget B, our cluster level Optimisation model is designed to select those clusters whose total cost does not exceed B while maximising the overall risk reduction. For instance, if B is set to 100,000 EUR, clusters with a relatively high average maintenance probability and low total cost will be prioritised. In our results in figure 7, Cluster 0, which has an average probability of 0.444286 across 7 segments and a total cost of only 1,400.00 EUR, represents a practical candidate for early maintenance action. In contrast, Cluster 3, with 10 segments but a significantly higher total cost of 79,960.02 EUR, may be deferred or selected only when additional budget becomes available. As a result, the selected clusters for intervention are {0, 2, 1, 3} in the order respectively, while cluster {4} is not selected due to its lower benefit the limited available budget. This approach allows us to allocate limited maintenance resources more effectively by targeting regions where the aggregated risk is highest relative to the cost. As a result, our framework provides actionable insights for proactive, cost-effective road maintenance planning in the Copenhagen area.

3.2.3 Integration of prediction and optimisation modules

The integration of the Prediction and Optimisation modules forms the backbone of the predictive maintenance framework. This modular workflow, illustrated in Figure 8, is designed to support data-driven and resource-efficient maintenance planning across road networks. The process begins with the **Prediction Module**, which collects heterogeneous data sources and applies infrastructure condition forecasting techniques. These predictions are then aggregated into spatial clusters to capture high-risk zones across the network. The output from the prediction phase is fed into the **Optimisation Module**, where a set of multi-objective criteria (e.g., cost, safety, environmental impact) is evaluated under resource constraints. The problem is formulated as a constrained integer programming model, where the goal is to select the most beneficial set of clusters for maintenance, subject to budgetary and operational constraints (e.g., labour, materials, time). This Optimisation process results in the generation of an **Optimal Maintenance Plan**, a prioritised schedule of interventions that maximises infrastructure value while maintaining serviceability and minimising resource expenditure.

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The integrated design ensures that high-risk areas are addressed proactively, supporting reliable, cost-effective, and sustainable road maintenance strategies.

Figure 8. A combination chart of prediction module and Optimisation module to finalise an optimal maintenance plan

The entire framework is adaptable, enabling updates based on new data, changing resource availability, and evolving maintenance priorities:

- Updating the Prediction Model: As new inspection data (e.g., IRI, MPD, SED, WD, CA) becomes available—either from scheduled surveys, mobile sensors, or Task 2.2 systems—the **Prediction Module** retrains or fine-tunes its models.
- Recomputing Risk Scores and Clusters: After model retraining, updated risk probabilities are computed for all road segments. These are then re-clustered using the DBSCAN algorithm to form new maintenance hotspots, reflecting the latest network condition
- Re-Optimisation Based on Updated Clusters: The updated clusters, along with their revised cost estimates and risk scores, are fed into the **Optimisation Module**. The integer programming model is re-run to produce a refreshed Optimal Maintenance Plan. This plan better reflects current infrastructure needs and available resources, ensuring that maintenance efforts are always targeted and efficient.
- Flexibility in Scheduling and Resource Planning: Because the system supports periodic updates (e.g., quarterly, bi-annually), planners can revisit the Optimisation as often as new data becomes available, making it easier to adapt to budget changes, new constraints, or shifts in strategic priorities.

Together, the Prediction and Optimisation modules provide a cohesive and scalable solution for intelligent infrastructure asset management within the EvoRoads project. These modules are currently being validated using datasets from the Copenhagen pilot, where urban road degradation and sensor-equipped vehicle data offer relevant use cases. The predictive component directly supports the city's need for early maintenance planning, while the optimisation layer aligns with prioritisation goals for resource allocation. While the third module currently lacks access to appropriate pilot data, we are addressing this gap by developing synthetic datasets that reflect typical urban degradation patterns.

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3.3 Additional modules to enhance the predictive maintenance model

In addition to the core functionality of the predictive maintenance model, several **additional modules** developed by our partners could significantly improve the system's capabilities. These modules, focusing on diverse aspects of road infrastructure monitoring, will contribute to enhancing the accuracy, efficiency, and adaptability of the predictive maintenance approach. These modules include Spatial Clustering for Pavement Condition Analysis from UAV, Synthetic Crack-Growth Dataset Preparation, and Road Risk Identification and Intervention Support Tool. By incorporating these **additional modules** into the predictive maintenance model, the system becomes more **comprehensive** and **adaptive**, improving its ability to predict and address road distress.

3.3.1 Spatial clustering for pavement condition analysis from UAVS

This section presents a spatial clustering methodology to identify zones of concentrated road surface deterioration. The method leverages the outputs of crack segmentation and pothole detection developed in Deliverable 2.1. By analysing the spatial co-location of defects, it supports a localized and priority-driven approach to pavement evaluation.

The approach departs from traditional scoring systems that average damage across entire segments (e.g., **PASER**, **PCI**), introducing a spatially sensitive layer capable of identifying high-risk zones based on defect clustering. This is crucial for early intervention and more effective allocation of maintenance resources.

Application

Contribution to Objective 2: Localized Infrastructure Assessment Using Clustering

The clustering methodology provides a refined spatial perspective of surface degradation. It detects zones where cracks occur in proximity and form critical deterioration zones. This allows:

- Detection of critical deterioration zones that are not visible through aggregate ratings
- More precise and proactive maintenance interventions
- Integration of cluster-based indicators into Pavement Management Systems (PMS)

Figure 9 High-Level Workflow

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From UAV-based inspection and deep learning-based detection to clustering, spatial metrics, and DBPCI scoring.

🕒 Datasets

The clustering system is built upon datasets developed in Task 2.1:

- 🕒 **Synthetic segmentation dataset:** Composed of UAV images with crack masks for training pixel-level segmentation models.
- 🕒 **Real object detection dataset:** Labelled images from UAV surveys over Cyprus roads, enhanced with RDD2022 data, capturing four damage types: longitudinal, transverse, alligator cracks, and potholes.

Each dataset includes scaling information that supports pixel-to-meter transformation for accurate spatial analysis of surface damage.

🕒 Preprocessing Analysis

The spatial clustering process includes the following steps:

- 🕒 **Defect localisation:** Extraction of crack and pothole centroids from model predictions
- 🕒 **Metric conversion:** Transformation of image coordinates into real-world distances using georeferencing metadata
- 🕒 **Distance computation:** Generation of pairwise distance matrices between all detected defects
- 🕒 **Noise filtering:** Exclusion of non-road regions and artifacts (e.g., vehicles, shadows)
- 🕒 **Proximity labelling:** Defects within defined distance thresholds are flagged for cluster formation

The output is a spatially enriched dataset prepared for clustering.

🕒 Tool Development

The developed tool integrates object detection and spatial clustering:

- 🕒 **Detection Models:** YOLOv11 variants for crack detection
- 🕒 **Clustering Method:** Based on unsupervised spatial grouping and custom proximity-based rules.
- 🕒 **Cluster-level Metrics:**
 - 🕒 Number of defects per cluster
 - 🕒 Average intra-cluster spacing
 - 🕒 Crack–pothole co-location frequency
 - 🕒 Severity-weighted scoring

A spatially informed condition index, the **Distance-Based Pavement Condition Index (DBPCI)**, has been introduced. It combines spatial intensity of detected defects, assigning each image or road segment a score based on clustering and anomaly co-location.

The following table maps surface condition ratings to clustering patterns and maintenance implications:

Table 4. surface condition ratings to clustering patterns and maintenance implications

RATING	SURFACE CONDITION	TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION	MAINTENANCE ACTION
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10	Excellent	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> None General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> New construction	Treatment measures: None
9	Excellent	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> None General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> Recent Overlay Like new	Treatment measures: None
8	Very Good	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> Transverse cracks <input type="checkbox"/> Spaced: => 12m General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> Recent Sealcoat	Treatment measures: Little or no maintenance
7	Good	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> Transverse cracks <input type="checkbox"/> Spaced: 3m-12m General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> First signs of aging	Treatment measures: Routine crack filling
6	Good	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> Longitudinal cracks <input type="checkbox"/> Spaced: <3m General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> Shows signs of aging	Treatment measures: Sealcoat
5	Fair	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> Longitudinal cracks <input type="checkbox"/> Transverse cracks <input type="checkbox"/> (<50% surface) General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> Surface aging	Treatment measures: Thin non-structural overlay (<50mm)
4	Fair	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> Longitudinal cracks <input type="checkbox"/> Transverse cracks <input type="checkbox"/> (>50% surface) General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> Surface aging and first signs of strengthening	Treatment measures: Structural overlay (>50mm)
3	Poor	Visible distress: <input type="checkbox"/> Closely spaced longitudinal and transverse cracks <input type="checkbox"/> Occasional potholes General Condition: <input type="checkbox"/> Needs patching and repair prior to major overlay.	Treatment measures: Milling and removal of deterioration extends the life of overlay

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2	Very Poor	Visible distress: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Potholes General Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1. Severe deterioration ○ 2. Needs reconstruction with extensive base repair 	Treatment measures: Pulverization of old pavement is effective
1	Failed	Visible distress: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Severe distress with extensive loss of surface integrity General Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Failed 	Treatment measures: Total reconstruction

○ Tool Validation

Validation of the clustering and scoring methodology is currently in progress. The system builds directly upon the crack and pothole detection results presented in Deliverable 2.1. These outputs have been used to extract defect coordinates and generate initial spatial clustering patterns. However, full correlation with expert assessments and segment-level condition ratings has not yet been completed.

Current status:

- Detection outputs (D2.1) integrated into spatial clustering workflow
- Clustering-based scoring tested on a subset of UAV images
- Surface condition indicators under refinement

Next steps:

- Complete proximity-based clustering analysis on the full annotated dataset
- Validate DBPCI scores against PASER ratings and manual expert assessments
- Finalise condition-to-rating decision rules and threshold logic

○ Summary

Deliverable 2.2 introduces a spatial clustering methodology to enhance UAV-based road condition monitoring. Unlike traditional pavement indices, which summarise condition across whole segments, this approach identifies concentrated damage zones through proximity-based logic and deep learning-based detection.

The combination of AI-powered crack/pothole detection, real-world distance mapping, and unsupervised clustering enables targeted insights that support smarter maintenance strategies. The proposed DBPCI offers a novel rating scheme that integrates clustering severity into standard road evaluation frameworks.

The system supports:

- Early identification of localized degradation
- Prioritisation of segments with intense defect clustering
- Decision-support for predictive maintenance and PMS integration

Future validation steps will confirm its operational value across broader road networks and help refine the index for deployment in real-world infrastructure management.

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3.3.2 Synthetic crack-growth dataset preparation

(Contributors: EUT)

To support the training of AI models for infrastructure condition monitoring, specifically in the context of crack detection and growth analysis, a series of synthetic images was generated to simulate the temporal evolution of road surface degradation. The primary objective of this dataset is to provide realistic and precisely labelled visual material that reflects how cracks form and evolve over time under real-world conditions. A process that is otherwise difficult to document systematically through traditional data collection due to the unpredictable and gradual nature of crack progression.

Figure 10. Screenshot of fSpy software for camera calibration and perspective (include focal lens, Deep of Focus “DoF” and orientation)

The generation process was carried out using the 3D modelling software *Blender*, where a digital twin of a deteriorated asphalt surface was created. To ensure geometric and perspective fidelity with real-world imagery, the virtual camera in Blender was calibrated using the software *fSpy* tool, which extracts focal length, orientation, and sensor alignment from a reference photograph (for more documental information please visit its [repository](#)). This calibration process, illustrated in Figure 10, enabled the synthetic camera to accurately replicate the viewpoint of a real-world scene, making the rendered images suitable for direct comparison, domain adaptation, or model fine-tuning tasks. The resulting camera configuration was imported into Blender and applied consistently across all frames in the sequence to maintain a fixed point of view throughout the crack growth simulation.

The evolution of the cracks was modelled procedurally using a custom shader composed of a Voronoi texture blended with a *Musgrave* fractal generator, both modulated via a *ColorRamp* node acting as a mask controller. The internal structure of this shader setup is shown in Figure 11.

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Crack Procedural Material – Hierarchical Node Map

Figure 11. Shader node structure used for procedural crack generation in Blender.

This configuration enabled the simulation of crack initiation, propagation, and coalescence over time. The output of the *ColorRamp* was simultaneously linked to a *Displacement* node, enabling geometric deformation of the surface mesh in accordance with the visual crack pattern. A driver-controlled parameter, **Crack_Spread**, was introduced and keyframed across seven intervals from 0 (initial micro-cracks) to 1 (fully developed fracture network)—to control temporal progression. The animated values used in this simulation are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5. Animated parameters controlling crack progression in Blender

Frame	Crack_Spread (Driver Value)	Crack Density	Crack Width	Displacement Scale	Notes
0	0	Very low	Hairline	0	Initial surface, barely visible cracks
1	0.15	Low	Narrow	0.001	Small isolated fractures
2	0.3	Moderate	Narrow	0.002	Beginning of propagation

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3	0.45	Moderate	Medium	0.003	Cracks begin to connect
4	0.6	High	Medium	0.004	Surface begins showing patterns
5	0.75	Very high	Medium-Wide	0.005	Fragmentation is evident
6	0.9	Dense	Wide	0.006	Nearly complete degradation
7	1	Full coverage	Wide	0.007	End state: crack network fully formed

A total of eight frames were rendered for each reference photograph, each representing a successive time step in the deterioration process. These frames were generated by linearly animating the Crack_Spread property from 0.00 to 1.00, with optional variation introduced through controlled randomisation of texture seeds to prevent repetitive visual patterns. Early frames depict sparse, fine cracks, whereas later stages exhibit dense, interconnected networks and visible surface fragmentation, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Cracks representation in a composition image. (Frame sequence)

Rendered outputs include both RGB images and pixel-level segmentation masks that define crack regions, thereby eliminating the need for manual annotation and ensuring full control over dataset consistency. An example of an RGB render and its corresponding mask is presented in Figure 13. Lighting conditions and backgrounds were standardised across all frames to enhance contrast and facilitate consistent model training and evaluation.

Figure 13. Mask image and composition image for segmentations models

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This synthetic dataset is particularly valuable for training temporal models such as convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTMs) or recurrent convolutional neural network (CNNs), which benefit from input sequences that reflect continuous physical progression. It also supports supervised learning configurations aimed at crack segmentation, severity classification, and predictive deterioration modelling. The dataset is currently being shared with partners involved in Task 2.3, who are developing AI-based tools for predictive maintenance. These synthetic samples serve to enrich real-world training datasets, particularly by covering edge cases and early-stage damage scenarios that are rarely captured in field data.

From a methodological standpoint, the use of procedural shading and animation enables full parameterisation of the simulation, including crack density, width, depth (via displacement), lighting angle, and asphalt roughness. This provides a versatile testbed not only for model training but also for robustness analysis, domain generalisation, and change detection algorithms.

However, whilst the simulations offer a high degree of control and visual realism, their fidelity is inherently constrained by the limitations of the software. The accuracy of the textures, the detail of the 3D surface models, and the procedural nature of the crack growth do not fully replicate the complex physical and environmental dynamics present in real-world degradation. Factors such as material heterogeneity, sub-surface cracking, moisture infiltration, and weather-induced erosion are not explicitly modelled. Moreover, the synthetic cracks, although visually convincing, follow algorithmic patterns that may lack the stochastic irregularities of real damage. These limitations should be carefully considered when using the dataset to train or evaluate AI models intended for deployment in uncontrolled environments. Consequently, combining these synthetic sequences with real-world annotated data remains essential for effective domain adaptation and generalisation.

3.3.3 Spatial road risk identification and intervention support tool

3.3.3.1 Accident data overview

In Deliverable D2.1, we outlined the development of an AI tool for road accident prediction based on historical data provided by our partners at CSI Piemonte. This dataset documents road accidents across the Piemonte region of Italy from 2016 to 2022. In this section, we demonstrate how the AI tool can be used by stakeholders, particularly within CSI Piemonte, to support predictive maintenance planning and data-driven decision-making.

The dataset comprises 3,516,774 records and 68 columns, offering annualised data for each road segment. These include accident counts (total, with injuries, and with fatalities), vehicle flow, road and municipal identifiers, and related administrative divisions. However, more granular contextual variables, such as exact accident timestamps, root causes (e.g. infrastructure vs. driver error), weather conditions, or road quality indicators, were not made available by CSI Piemonte due to privacy and security reasons. Despite these limitations, the available data enables meaningful analyses of spatial and temporal accident patterns.

3.3.3.2 Overview

The AI tool analyses historical accident data to assess the risk of each road segment and support targeted intervention planning. To better account for road intersections, crossings, and other spatial discontinuities, where accidents may be dispersed across closely connected segments, the tool evaluates *thickened* road segments, meaning each segment is augmented with accident data from neighbouring segments within a 20-metre radius, see D2.1 for details.

Risk is quantified in four main ways. First, by measuring the **accident trend** of each thickened road segment over the seven-year period (2016–2022), using a linear estimation method that captures whether accidents have been increasing, decreasing or remaining stable. Having identified the trend, we scale it to take values between 0 to 1, where 1 corresponds to the highest increasing trend and 0 the lowest.

Second, each road segment is assigned to a **risk cluster** through Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) clustering, based on the total number of accidents, accidents with injuries, accidents with fatalities, the number of injured individuals, and the **PU - PUBLIC**

number of deaths across all years. The model assigns each segment to one of six discrete clusters (0 to 5) and provides also the probability of membership to each of the clusters. For each road segment, its cluster and its probability of belonging to that cluster can both be used as measures of risk; we use the former to identify high-risk road segments and the latter to form the static risk cluster. It should be noted that, in contrast to Deliverable D2.1, which applied a 4-cluster approach, in this deliverable we use 6 risk clusters to enable more fine-grained differentiation, particularly among segments with a high frequency of recurring incidents.

Third, a **static risk cluster** is derived by combining the discrete cluster assignment and the associated membership probability into a single continuous value. To do this, each cluster is mapped to a specific numeric range; Cluster 0 corresponds to [0, 2], Cluster 1 to [2.1, 4], Cluster 2 to [4.1, 6], Cluster 3 to [6.1, 8], Cluster 4 to [8.1, 10], and Cluster 5 to [10.1, 12]. The probability of belonging to the assigned cluster is then scaled within the corresponding range to obtain a continuous representation of clusters. For instance, a road segment assigned to Cluster 4 with a probability of 0.8 would receive a static risk cluster of 9.6. This metric is then scaled, similarly to the trend, to range from 0 to 1.

Fourth, a **combined score** is produced by averaging the trend (scaled) and the static risk cluster (scaled). This gives a balanced indicator that accounts for both the segment's historical accident dynamics (i.e. trend) and its static risk profile (i.e. static risk cluster). Currently, the combined score gives equal weight (50/50) to the trend and the static risk cluster, but these weights can be adapted to reflect stakeholder priorities. For example, if the stakeholders prefer to primarily consider highly increasing accident locations rather than static high-risk areas, they can adjust the weight to 0.7 for trend and 0.3 for static risk cluster.

Table 6. an illustrative example of the metrics produced by the tool

ROAD SEGMENT	TREND (SCALED)	RISK CLUSTER (GMM)	ASSIGNED CLUSTER MEMBERSHIP PROBABILITY	PROBABILITY OF HIGHEST RISK CLUSTER	STATIC RISK CLUSTER (SCALED)	COMBINED SCORE (0.5*SCALED TREND AND 0.5*SCALED STATIC RISK CLUSTER)
004BDE73-73D8-4232-9000-B447D5897261	0.5625	5	0.9999	0.9999	1.000	0.8147
010CACED-9FA2-55D3-E054-0003BA0F36E6	0.5598	2	1.000	0.0000	0.500	0.4285

3.3.3.3 Functionalities

The AI tool offers a range of functionalities to support road safety analysis and decision-making across different spatial levels, including municipalities, administrative extensions, and grouped road segments. These functionalities allow users to extract insights and prioritise interventions flexibly, depending on their specific geographic focus or preferred grouping.

Key functionalities include:

1. **Ranking of road segments by static risk cluster, by trend, or by combined score:** Users can retrieve the top-N most critical segments (e.g. top 5, 10, etc.) within any chosen geographic unit based on the metric of interest.
2. **Visualisation of risk and trend clusters:** The tool uses GMM to group road segments into 10 clusters based on the accident trend and 6 clusters based on accident severity and frequency indicators (number of injuries, deaths,

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etc.). The emerging clusters can be visualised on a map, offering a quick overview of areas with increasing or stable patterns, or high static risk levels.

These features are designed to be modular and adaptable, enabling evidence-based road safety planning across different levels of aggregation and geographic focus.

3.3.3.4 Example use cases

Here we present three indicative use cases showing how the AI tool can be used for making interventions, some of which may be related to predictive maintenance. These examples include:

1. **Prioritisation of High-Risk Road Segments per Municipality**
2. **Identifying High-Need Municipalities for Budget Allocation**
3. **Risk Overview by Road Group Across the Regional Network**

Those use cases are analysed below in turn.

Use Case 1: Prioritisation of High-Risk Road Segments per Municipality

In many municipalities, local stakeholders are interested in identifying which road segments should be prioritised for safety interventions. This is particularly relevant in contexts where budgets are limited and must be allocated efficiently to maximise the impact on reducing road accidents and improving public safety.

The tool provides a range of functionalities to support such decision-making. Below are three indicative scenarios based on the municipality of Vercelli, demonstrating how stakeholders might use the tool to inform risk-based prioritisation strategies.

Scenario 1:

The stakeholders aim to identify the 10 highest static risk road segments within a given municipality (e.g. Vercelli). This ranking is based on the static risk cluster, which integrates both the severity of accidents (including total accidents, injuries, fatalities, number of injured individuals, and deaths) and the probability of a segment belonging to the cluster to which it is assigned, providing a continuous and fine-grained risk assessment. For this purpose, the stakeholders use the functionality 1st from the description above.

To complement this, the tool also allows stakeholders to visualise on the map all road segments grouped into the sixth risk cluster (high static risk cluster), derived from a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM). This enables users to quickly identify all segments that have a large number of accidents across all years and gain immediate spatial insight beyond the top-ranked segments. This is achieved using the 2nd functionality.

Top 10 segments identified:

'413F8D0F-B811-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-EB60-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-EA5C-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E944-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E926-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-B023-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-B771-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E921-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E91C-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-B366-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6'

Top 10 segments identified on the map:

Figure 14. Segments identified on the map

All high static risk segments identified on the map:

Figure 15. High static risk segments

Scenario 2:

Stakeholders aim to identify the 10 road segments with the fastest-growing number of accidents over time, using functionality 1. Similarly with the previous scenario, they can also see all the high-trend road segments on map using the 2nd functionality. This enables early intervention in areas where risks are escalating, even if the absolute number of past incidents is still relatively low.

Top 10 trend-increasing segments:

'413F8D0F-AE9D-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-C68A-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-C761-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-CFB8-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-D7F1-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-EC73-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-F5F6-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-C815-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E52F-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E8EA-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6'

All high-trend segments:

Figure 16. All high-trend segments

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Note: The tool possesses two metrics describing the trend of accidents for each road segment. Those are the **trend**, as calculated based on the linear method discussed in D2.1, and the **trend cluster**, which is calculated by applying Gaussian Mixture Models Clustering (GMM) on the estimated trend variable and setting the number of clusters to 10. The former is used for analysis and ranking purposes, since it offers more detailed information regarding the change of accidents over the years, while the latter is used primarily for visualisation, offering an immediate overview of regional trend patterns in map-based outputs.

Scenario 3:

This scenario supports stakeholders in making informed decisions by considering both the long-term accident burden (i.e. static risk cluster) and its temporal evolution (i.e. trend). For this purpose, they can use functionality 1 for ranking road segments based on the combined score. By using this indicator, stakeholders can identify the top 10 segments with the highest overall risk dynamics, enabling more comprehensive and strategic planning.

Top 10 segments by combined score:

'413F8D0F-E949-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E66A-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-D4C7-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-CC11-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-D003-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-BDD9-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E345-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-B7A3-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E17E-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6', '413F8D0F-E8EF-5FFE-E054-0003BA0F36E6'

Use Case 2: Identifying High-Need Municipalities for Budget Allocation

Stakeholders responsible for regional or municipal budget planning may wish to prioritise funding for communities with the most urgent road safety needs. To support such decisions, the tool offers multiple perspectives on risk (i.e. static, dynamic, and combination of the two) across municipalities. Below are five illustrative scenarios highlighting how stakeholders can extract meaningful insights from the data.

Scenario 1:

Identify the top five municipalities with the greatest number of road segments classified in the highest static risk cluster, using functionality 1.

'TORINO', 'NOVARA', 'ASTI', 'ALESSANDRIA', 'CUNEO'

Scenario 2:

Determine the top five municipalities where the percentage of road segments in the highest risk cluster is the largest.

'LA GRANGIA', 'REALA', 'Fara Novarese', 'PONTE ROCCA', 'Biandrate'

Scenario 3:

Identify the top five municipalities based on the average upward trend in accident rates over time, using functionality 1.

'Carisio', 'COSSOMBRATO', 'SANTO STEFANO', 'RUATA', 'VEROLENGO'

Scenario 4:

Highlight the top ten municipalities by considering the combined scores, using functionality 1.

'PONTE ROCCA', 'Rivoli', "Diano d'Alba", 'Fara Novarese', 'LA GRANGIA', 'REALA', 'Biandrate', 'Rivalta Bormida', 'NIVETTA', 'Monastero di Vasco'

Scenario 5:

They would like to access information regarding the total number of road segments, the number and the percentage of segments identified to be high risk (e.g. assigned in the highest static risk cluster), the number and the percentage of

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segments identified to be high trend (e.g. assigned in the highest trend cluster), the average static risk cluster (scaled), the average trend (scaled), and the average combined score, for the 15 municipalities that have the higher road network (i.e. higher number of distinct road segments).

Provide a detailed overview for the 15 municipalities with the highest number of distinct road segments, including:

- Total number of segments
- Number and percentage of high static risk segments
- Number and percentage of high-trend segments
- Average static risk cluster (scaled from 0 to 1)
- Average accident trend (scaled from 0 to 1)
- Average combined score

This summary enables strategic resource allocation by balancing network size, emerging trends, and known risk levels.

Risk information for the top 15 municipalities in terms of number of road segments:

municipality	nof_road_segments	nof_high_risk_segments	nof_high_trend_segments	high_risk_percentage	high_trend_percentage	average_trend_scaled	average_static_risk_cluster_scaled	average_combined_score
TORINO	21334	5035	113	23.6	0.5	0.559	0.302	0.431
ASTI	13218	648	15	4.9	0.1	0.562	0.058	0.310
VERCELLI	5722	466	7	8.1	0.1	0.562	0.085	0.323
NOVARA	4116	723	21	17.6	0.5	0.561	0.213	0.387
CUNEO	3449	467	10	13.5	0.3	0.562	0.162	0.362
TORTONA	3397	258	2	7.6	0.1	0.562	0.092	0.327
MONDOVI'	3065	139	2	4.5	0.1	0.562	0.053	0.308
FOSSANO	3059	182	3	5.9	0.1	0.562	0.072	0.317
MONCALIERI	3058	331	4	10.8	0.1	0.562	0.131	0.346
RIVOLI	2843	328	7	11.5	0.2	0.561	0.141	0.351
BORGO SAN DALMAZZO	2789	72	1	2.6	0.0	0.562	0.030	0.296
ALESSANDRIA	2667	582	9	21.8	0.3	0.561	0.268	0.414
BRA	2665	206	2	7.7	0.1	0.562	0.096	0.329
ALBA	2650	193	7	7.3	0.3	0.562	0.086	0.324
SETTIMO TORINESE	2650	275	5	10.4	0.2	0.562	0.121	0.342

Figure 17. Risk information for the top 15 municipalities in terms of number of road segments

Use Case 3: Risk Overview by Road Group Across the Regional Network

This use case analyses a scenario in which stakeholders from CSI Piemonte seek broad visibility into accident patterns across the entire road network. Specifically, they may wish to review accident statistics for road segments that belong to large road groups, as indicated by the 'group_strada' column in the dataset.

Scenario 1:

The user can retrieve detailed statistics for the top 10 road groups with the largest number of segments. These statistics include:

- Number of road segments
- Number and percentage of high static risk segments
- Number and percentage of high-trend segments
- Average composite risk (scaled from 0 to 1)
- Average accident trend (scaled from 0 to 1)
- Average combined score

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Risk information for the top 10 road groups in terms of number of road segments:

road_group	nof_road_segments	nof_high_risk_segments	nof_high_trend_segments	high_risk_percentage	high_trend_percentage	average_trend_scaled	average_static_risk_cluster_scaled	average_combined_score
fk3_70652	886	88	4	9.9	0.5	0.561	0.125	0.343
fk3_50061	880	150	3	17.0	0.3	0.562	0.204	0.383
fk3_60050	796	81	0	10.2	0.0	0.562	0.117	0.339
fk3_50003	757	104	1	13.7	0.1	0.562	0.175	0.369
fk3_50054	751	75	2	10.0	0.3	0.560	0.137	0.349
fk3_50073	723	119	3	16.5	0.4	0.562	0.192	0.377
fk3_50069	695	134	2	19.3	0.3	0.562	0.233	0.397
fk2_52165	660	6	0	0.9	0.0	0.562	0.011	0.287
fk3_50053	657	133	2	20.2	0.3	0.561	0.251	0.406
fk3_50074	617	97	1	15.7	0.2	0.562	0.185	0.373

Figure 18. Risk information for the top 10 road groups in terms of number of road segments

Scenario 2:

The user can visualise the top 100 road groups with the highest number of segments directly on the map. Each segment is color-coded based on its combined score, providing an intuitive spatial representation of risk across the network.

Road segments belonging to the top 100 road groups identified on the map:

Figure 19. Road segments belonging to the top 100 road groups identified on the map

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3.3.3.5 Integration and future expansion

The next step is to integrate the AI-powered tool into the website used by our stakeholders at CSI Piemonte. This will allow them to visualise the results of the current accident data analysis directly through an accessible platform. Initially, the focus will be on presenting the insights generated through our existing methods. However, the long-term goal is to make the tool's functionalities directly available through interfaces, enabling stakeholders to customise queries and retrieve tailored results based on their specific needs.

In parallel, this analysis is intended to encourage stakeholders to provide more detailed information, such as accident causes, pavement conditions, territorial or weather characteristics, and precise accident timestamps rather than yearly aggregates. Although such data has not yet been shared due to privacy concerns, we hope that future collaborations will allow access to these critical variables, enabling deeper analyses and expanded tool capabilities. Also, if other risk metrics are made available (for instance metrics related to predictive maintenance), they can be also considered in the combined score, to provide even more detailed information about the accident risk for the geographic area of interest. Another envisioned step is to develop a dynamic system that continuously receives new accident data, automatically updates its algorithms, and returns updated insights. In such a scenario, and with richer input data, the tool could be enhanced and offer even more advanced functionalities for evidence-based decision support.

3.4 Post-impact repair analysis and feedback

The **Post-Impact Repair Analysis and Feedback** module serves as a vital component in ensuring continuous improvement and adaptive learning within the predictive maintenance system. Once maintenance actions have been performed, this module evaluates the **effectiveness of interventions**, analyses discrepancies between expected and actual outcomes, and feeds this information back into the model training pipeline. This not only enhances model reliability over time but also provides infrastructure managers with valuable insights into maintenance performance.

3.4.1 Repair effectiveness evaluation

Each repaired segment is re-evaluated using **post-maintenance inspection data**. The module measures the change in pavement condition through several key indicators. Improvements are calculated by comparing values before and after repair:

- Reduction in International Roughness Index (IRI): $\Delta_{IRI} = IRI_{before} - IRI_{after}$
- Reduction in Mean Profile Depth (MPD): $\Delta_{MPD} = MPD_{before} - MPD_{after}$
- Reduction in Straight Edge Deviation (SED): $\Delta_{SED} = SED_{before} - SED_{after}$
- Reduction in Wire Deviation (WD): $\Delta_{WD} = WD_{before} - WD_{after}$
- Reduction in Cracking Area (CA): $\Delta_{CA} = CA_{before} - CA_{after}$

These metrics collectively assess structural and surface improvements resulting from maintenance, capturing both ride quality and surface uniformity.

3.4.2 Impact assessment metrics

To synthesise multiple indicators into a comprehensive evaluation, the module computes a composite **Repair Score (RS)** for each segment in time t :

$$RS_i(t) = w_1 \cdot \Delta_{IRI}(t) + w_2 \cdot \Delta_{MPD}(t) + w_3 \cdot \Delta_{SED}(t) + w_4 \cdot \Delta_{WD}(t) + w_5 \cdot \Delta_{CA}(t)$$

Where:

- w_1 through w_5 are weighting coefficients based on the relative importance of each metric,
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- The weights can be adjusted depending on road classification, use case (urban vs. highway), or national standards.

These values help infrastructure managers assess not only whether repairs were performed, but whether they achieved the intended performance targets in terms of surface quality, safety, and durability.

3.4.3 Feedback mechanism for future optimisation

Once the repair outcomes are quantified, the results are used to adjust the predictive models in a feedback loop. The system identifies:

- **False Positives:** Segments flagged for maintenance that showed little or no improvement, indicating overly sensitive thresholds.
- **False Negatives:** Segments not flagged but later repaired or failed, indicating underestimation of degradation risk.

These cases are used to:

- Refine anomaly detection thresholds,
- Adjust feature weights in the classification model,
- Rebalance training datasets,
- Improve generalisation through model fine-tuning or re-training.

At the moment, there has been no EvoRoads pilot site committed to providing real-world data suitable for validating the feedback-driven optimisation module. We recognise this as a current limitation and are actively exploring mitigation options. These include the generation of synthetic datasets to simulate multi-year maintenance outcomes, as well as exploratory discussions with pilot teams to assess future integration opportunities. By acknowledging this constraint early, we aim to remain adaptive and ensure that the module remains compatible with downstream deployment and demonstration.

4 On-the-edge and connected road safety systems

4.1 Overview

This section provides a general overview of the two core components developed in this task: HAIM (Hazard-Aware Infrastructure Monitoring) and AIRHD (Artificial Intelligence for Road Hazard Detection). While each system is designed to operate independently, they are also intended to complement one another within an integrated road monitoring strategy.

HAIM is a physical device focused on collecting critical environmental and structural data from road infrastructure. It incorporates multiple sensors to measure key parameters such as temperature, object presence, and road surface characteristics. Designed for outdoor deployment, HAIM operates autonomously and is adaptable to different monitoring scenarios, providing reliable data to support infrastructure assessment and maintenance planning.

AIRHD, in contrast, is a software-based system that applies artificial intelligence and computer vision techniques to analyse video feeds from fixed surveillance cameras. Its primary role is to detect hazards such as road debris, vehicles, animals, or degraded conditions using real-time image processing and machine learning algorithms. The system is optimised for performance across different computing environments, allowing it to scale from GPU-enabled platforms to more modest CPU-based setups.

Together, HAIM and AIRHD offer complementary perspectives: one through direct physical measurement, and the other through intelligent interpretation of visual information.

The HAIM system is designed to be deployed along the roadside, positioned at ground level to directly monitor surface-level conditions through embedded sensors. In contrast, the AIRHD system is intended to integrate with existing roadside video surveillance infrastructure, typically installed at elevated positions on the lateral boundaries of the road.

4.2 Hazard-Aware Infrastructure Monitoring (HAIM) tool

The HAIM device being developed is designed to measure a series of key variables of interest, agreed upon with IDIADA, that are essential for assessing road conditions and monitoring vehicle activity. These measurements include asphalt temperature and ambient temperature, which will be captured using an infrared optical sensor. Additionally, an ultrasonic sensor will be used to determine which lane the vehicles are traveling in. To evaluate the characteristics of the asphalt surface, a LIDAR sensor will scan the road section and generate 2D maps that allow for the identification of specific surface features, such as wear or irregularities.

The entire system will be managed by an embedded controller, specifically the Jetson Orin Nano (JNO), which will handle the acquisition and processing of data using linear algorithms. These algorithms will enable the system to interpret sensor outputs efficiently and support real-time analysis. The necessary electronics will be integrated to ensure proper functionality and coordination between components.

The HAIM device is ideally designed for deployment in **rural road environments**, where limited monitoring infrastructure often leads to delayed response times and a higher risk of accidents. By providing continuous data collection and analysis, the system can be integrated with warning and alert mechanisms aimed at notifying road users or relevant authorities about potentially hazardous conditions. In doing so, HAIM contributes to enhancing road safety and supporting timely preventive measures in less supervised areas.

4.2.1 Electronic components

The following table (Table 7) presents a breakdown of each electronic component of the HAIM device, including its power consumption, the type of variable it provides, the parameter it measures, and its measurement frequency

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Table 7. Electronic components characteristics

PARAMETER	TECHNOLOGY	TYPE	SAMPLING RATE	WATTS	TYPE OF DATA
Asphalt Temperature	GY-906	Optical sensor (Infrared sensor)	Every 30 min	0.075	INT / String (DB)
Environmental Temperature	GY-906	Optical sensor (Infrared sensor)	Every 10 min	0.075	INT / String (DB)
Debris (rocks, plastic pieces, tree branches), water puddle/accumulation	RPLIDAR A3M8 / STL-27L	Optical Sensor (Laser)	Every 30min or 1h	2.5 / 1.45	INT / String (DB)
Vehicles detection	JSN-SR04T	Ultrasonic	Every 0,1 seconds	0.04	INT / String (DB)
Data controller	Jetson Orin Nano	Microcontroller unit CPU/GPU		25	
Compass	GY-273	Magnetic sensor	Every 5 seconds	0.04	INT / String
GPS	NEO-6M / u-blox	GPS – Communication	1 times / day	0.05	INT / String (DB)

4.2.1.1 Jetson Nano Orin

The Jetson Nano Orin is a high-performance development platform created by [NVIDIA](#), specifically designed for AI and edge computing applications. With a power consumption of only 25 watts, it offers an energy-efficient option for projects that require high performance, such as computer vision, robotics, and real-time data processing. This feature makes it ideal for environments where energy efficiency is crucial without compromising performance. Additionally, the JNO is equipped with hardware optimised for running complex AI algorithms, enabling advanced tasks such as image analysis, object detection, and data processing from sensors without the need for servers or cloud computing. This not only improves the speed of applications but also reduces latency, which is essential for projects requiring immediate responses.

Figure 20. Jetson Nano Orin Device – Image from Nvidia

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The system is programmable in several popular languages, including Python and C++, and is fully compatible with AI and computer vision frameworks like YOLO used by [TensorFlow](#), [PyTorch](#), and [OpenCV](#). Figure 20 shows the JNO device. This flexibility allows developers to integrate and customise machine learning algorithms and neural networks easily and efficiently.

Additionally, the JNO offers extensive connectivity with various sensors and devices, including high-definition cameras, LiDAR sensors, ultrasonic sensors, and more. This enables it to adapt to a wide range of projects, from industrial automation to infrastructure monitoring and autonomous vehicles. Thanks to its ability to manage multiple sensors and its capacity to perform parallel core processes, JNO is the perfect choice for projects requiring real-time data processing and efficient energy management.

Several scientific studies have demonstrated the versatility and performance of the JNO in a wide range of applications. In the article *AI on the Road: NVIDIA Jetson Nano-Powered Computer Vision-Based System for Real-Time Pedestrian and Priority Sign Detection*, a real-time computer vision system is described for detecting pedestrians and priority signs, using the Jetson Nano to process images and improve road safety (MDPI) [1]. Additionally, in a *Novel Smart System with JNO for Remote Insect Monitoring*, a remote insect monitoring system is presented, utilising object detection models and the Jetson Nano to facilitate agricultural management and environmental conservation [2].

On the other hand, in [3], the study *Benchmarking Deep Learning Models on NVIDIA Jetson Nano for Real-Time Systems* analyses the performance of deep learning models on the Jetson Nano, focusing on inference speed for image classification and action detection in video. Likewise, *Performance Evaluation of the Nvidia Jetson Nano Through a Real-Time Machine Learning Application* evaluates its performance in real-time machine learning applications, specifically in identifying and counting vehicles in the city of Quito, Ecuador [4]. Finally, the article *Face Mask Detection Using Deep Learning on NVIDIA Jetson Nano* presents a real-time face mask detection solution implemented on the Jetson Nano, contributing to public health measures during the COVID-19 pandemic [5]. These studies highlight how the JNO can be effectively applied to a wide range of real-time projects requiring both edge data processing and low energy consumption for the EvoRoads project.

4.2.1.2 GY-906 temperature sensor

The [GY-906](#) (Figure 21) is a temperature sensor commonly used in various applications, such as environmental monitoring, industrial automation, and weather forecasting. This sensor operates based on the thermistor principle, where the resistance of the thermistor changes with temperature. The GY-906 sensor can measure temperatures within a specified range, typically from -40°C to 125°C , with reasonable accuracy. It provides an analogue output that can be read by a microcontroller, such as an Arduino or Raspberry Pi, for real-time temperature measurement. The sensor uses a voltage divider circuit to produce a voltage that varies linearly with the temperature, which can then be processed by an analogue-to-digital converter (ADC) to determine the temperature value.

Figure 21. GY-906 Optical temperature sensor

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Due to its simplicity and cost-effectiveness, the GY-906 temperature sensor is popular in both hobbyist projects and industrial applications. It can be easily integrated into a variety of systems that require precise temperature monitoring, such as heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, weather stations, and even environmental sensors for smart homes. The sensor is powered by a 5V supply, making it compatible with most microcontrollers and embedded systems. One of the key benefits of the GY-906 is its reliability and ease of use, making it an ideal choice for developers who need to monitor temperature in real-time without complex setup. Additionally, its small size and low power consumption make it an efficient sensor for battery-powered applications or IoT systems where space and energy are limited. Overall, the GY-906 temperature sensor is a valuable component in any project that requires accurate and reliable temperature data.

Below is the type of data that is expected to be obtained with the sensor, once integrated into the system.

ID: Module identificatory (Ex.: [2]) DATE: UTC +0 format. Format: YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss (Ex.: [2024-10-18 10:15:32])

Temperature: Represented in °C (Ex.: [21.5])

4.2.1.3 RPLIDAR A3

The **RPLIDAR A3** sensor (Figure 22 left) offers exceptional accuracy and versatility in mapping and object detection, making it an ideal choice for many advanced projects. However, if a different LiDAR solution is required, the **STL-27L** sensor (Figure 22 right) is another great option to consider. The STL-27L is a compact and cost-effective 2D LiDAR sensor designed for similar applications as the RPLIDAR A3 but offers a more affordable alternative. While it may not have the same maximum scanning range as the RPLIDAR A3, the STL-27L still delivers reliable performance and is suitable for projects where budget constraints or space limitations are more significant factors.

The STL-27L features a 360-degree scanning ability with a scanning range typically between 6 to 8 meters, depending on environmental factors. This sensor also operates using a 5V power supply and communicates through UART or I2C, making it easy to integrate with a variety of embedded platforms like the Raspberry Pi, Arduino, and other microcontroller-based systems. Despite its lower range, the STL-27L is an excellent solution for applications such as indoor robotics, basic mapping tasks, and navigation where the required range does not exceed its capabilities. With a scanning rate of up to 5000 samples per second, it provides sufficient data density for basic obstacle avoidance and environment mapping, especially in confined spaces. While the RPLIDAR A3 is well-suited for large-scale mapping and high-accuracy applications, the STL-27L offers a more compact, lower-cost option that still maintains essential LiDAR functionality. Whether for smaller, more specific applications or for those working on a tight budget, the STL-27L sensor serves as a reliable tool that can still meet many of the needs of roboticists, developers, and engineers. Additionally, its relatively simple integration and ease of use make it a viable choice for prototype projects or those exploring the potential of LiDAR technology.

Figure 22. LiDAR sensors. Left RPLIDAR, Right STL-27L Lidar. source Robotshop

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LiDAR technology has proven to be an effective tool for detecting and analysing road features, such as lane markings. A notable example is the study titled "Efficient and Robust Lane Marking Extraction from Mobile LiDAR Point Clouds" [6], where mobile LiDAR systems were used to gather detailed road data. The researchers developed an efficient framework for automatically extracting lane markings from 3D LiDAR data, capable of handling a wide range of road geometries. Additionally, they proposed a restricted RANdom Sampling and Consensus (**RANSAC**) segmentation that extracts road surfaces in the absence of curb structures, accounting for road curvature and slope changes. This approach allowed for more precise extraction of lane markings, even in areas with worn or partially erased lane markings.

The results obtained in this study demonstrated that the proposed methodology outperformed previous approaches in terms of accuracy and robustness, particularly in complex road conditions. The ability to extract lane markings efficiently and accurately is critical for applications such as high-definition map creation for autonomous vehicles, infrastructure maintenance management, and improving road safety. Implementing LiDAR systems in road data collection allows for more detailed and accurate assessments of road conditions, facilitating informed decision-making in infrastructure planning and maintenance. Given the demonstrated success of LiDAR technology in studies like the one mentioned, it is considered an ideal option for projects requiring road feature detection and analysis. The ability of LiDAR sensors to provide accurate, real-time data is essential for applications demanding high precision and reliability, such as autonomous navigation and efficient infrastructure management [7].

4.2.1.4 Ultrasonic JSN-SR04T

Figure 23 shows the **JSN-SR04T**. It is a versatile ultrasonic sensor that operates on the principles of sound waves to measure distances, offering significant improvements over its predecessor, the HC-SR04. With a detection range of 0.2 meters to 4 meters and a high level of accuracy, this sensor is widely used for applications requiring precise distance measurements. The JSN-SR04T emits a sound pulse and measures the time it takes for the pulse to return after hitting an object, enabling it to calculate the distance. One of its most notable features is its enhanced waterproof and dustproof design, which ensures reliable performance even in harsh environments, such as wet or humid conditions. This makes it particularly useful in outdoor applications like obstacle detection for robotics, liquid level sensing in tanks, and environmental monitoring in weather stations. The sensor operates on a 5V power supply and uses a simple digital interface for communication, consisting of a trigger pin to initiate measurements and an echo pin to receive the reflected pulse. This ease of integration with microcontrollers like Arduino, Raspberry Pi, and other embedded systems makes the JSN-SR04T a popular choice for a wide variety of projects, from DIY robotics to industrial automation.

Figure 23. Ultrasonic Sensor. Source Robotshop

The JSN-SR04T has proven to be a reliable and cost-effective solution for distance sensing across many industries, particularly in applications where real-time measurements and environmental resistance are critical. Its waterproof and dustproof characteristics ensure that it continues to operate in challenging conditions, offering precise data even when exposed to moisture, dust, or debris. This has made it an essential component in robotic navigation, allowing robots to

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safely avoid obstacles in complex environments. Additionally, the sensor has found widespread use in autonomous vehicles, smart home systems, and inventory management, where it can be employed for tasks such as automated stock counting or material level monitoring in tanks and silos. Its affordability and simplicity also make it a preferred choice for scientific and engineering applications that require accurate distance measurements, such as environmental monitoring for flood prediction systems or water conservation efforts. With its adaptability, reliability, and ease of use, the JSN-SR04T ultrasonic sensor continues to be a valuable tool for developers and engineers across various fields.

Below is the type of data that is expected to be obtained with the sensor, once integrated into the system.

ID: Module identificatory (Ex.: [2]) DATE: UTC +0 format. Format: YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss (Ex.: [2024-10-18 10:15:32])

Vehicles: IN DISCUSSION)

4.2.1.5 Electronics supporting components

The **28BYJ-48 stepper motor** is widely used for its low cost, simplicity, and capability to rotate precisely in small increments, making it ideal for applications requiring controlled rotational movement. This motor operates using a set of coils that receive pulses of current, causing the motor to step through discrete positions. The 28BYJ-48 is controlled by the ULN2003 driver board, which allows the microcontroller to send signals to the motor. This combination provides precise control over the motor's movement, enabling it to rotate the RPLIDAR A3 sensor with the accuracy needed for detailed surface scanning. This setup will be used to rotate the LiDAR sensor over the surface, allowing for the generation of high-resolution surface maps. By capturing data from different rotational angles, the system can reconstruct a 2D image of the scanned area based on the LiDAR point cloud and intensity values. The collected data will be processed to generate visual representations of the surface, enabling the detection of road imperfections, obstacles, and other structural features essential for applications such as road mapping and infrastructure inspection.

To enhance the spatial awareness of the system, a GPS module (**NEO-6M / u-blox**) and a digital compass (**GY-273**) will also be integrated. The GPS module provides precise geographic coordinates of each scanned point, allowing the system to geolocate all collected data in real-world coordinates. Meanwhile, the GY-273 digital compass, based on the HMC5883L sensor, enables orientation tracking of the device, ensuring that each LiDAR scan is accurately referenced to the device's heading. This integration of positional and directional data is crucial for mapping applications and for correlating physical measurements with spatial context.

To control the 28BYJ-48 stepper motor, the ULN2003 driver board acts as an intermediary between the motor and the microcontroller, converting logic-level signals into the necessary current pulses to drive the motor's coils. This driver is straightforward to integrate and is commonly used in prototyping and low-power applications. DuPont jumper cables will be used to connect the stepper motor, driver board, and other modules, offering flexibility and ease of adjustment during development and testing. Additional electronic components include a regulated 5V power supply to provide sufficient current for the stepper motor and driver, ensuring efficient and stable operation of the scanning mechanism. The combined use of the stepper motor, LiDAR, orientation sensors (GPS and compass), and essential wiring results in a robust, compact, and cost-effective platform for accurate LiDAR-based surface mapping in mobile or stationary deployments.

4.2.2 HAIM design and specification

The prototyping of the device will be carried out using CAD design software, such as **SolidWorks**, which allows for the creation of accurate and detailed 3D models of all the device's components before manufacturing. SolidWorks is a key tool in ensuring that each part fits efficiently and functionally within the overall structure of the device. The device will consist of a main housing that will serve as the central structure where the various system components, including electronic and mechanical parts, will be mounted. It has been considered that the device will be installed on the roadside of rural roads, and the design has therefore been tailored to suit this specific environment. The housing will not only have a structural role but will also protect the internal components, ensuring their safety and proper functioning in various operational conditions. For the fabrication of the housing and mechanical parts, PLA (polylactic acid) will be used, a

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material commonly employed in 3D printing due to its ease of use, accessibility, and properties like biodegradability. In this initial approach, additive manufacturing via 3D printing will be chosen, as it allows for quick prototyping without the need for costly manufacturing tools. 3D printing offers the advantage of creating complex geometries that would be difficult to achieve with other traditional methods. Additionally, this technique facilitates rapid design iteration, enabling efficient adjustments to the structure if needed. The use of PLA is suitable at this early stage of prototyping as it is durable enough for functional testing, although other more advanced materials may be considered in later stages depending on the specific needs of the device. This approach not only speeds up the prototyping process but also helps optimise costs, allowing for multiple tests and improvements without large investments.

4.2.2.1 Device parts

4.2.2.1.1 Case

The main case will house all the previously mentioned components, except for the LiDAR sensor, which will be mounted on top of the structure to be supported by the cooling system component. This design ensures that the LiDAR sensor can be securely placed without obstructing the airflow or the cooling process for the Jetson Nano Orin (JNO). The cooling component is strategically placed to help dissipate heat effectively, and by supporting the LiDAR sensor on this piece, the system can optimise space and airflow while maintaining thermal efficiency. The overall structure of the device will be carefully designed to allow for the necessary components to be integrated while ensuring proper heat dissipation. The first designs for this section of the device can be seen in Figure 24, showing the layout and specifications. Figure 25 shows the top cover of the housing, which is responsible for enclosing the entire device while keeping the electronic components protected.

Figure 24. case A sketch

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Figure 25. case B sketch

Additionally, the first assembly of the electronic components into the case has been completed, as shown in Figure 26. This gives us a clear idea of how the device is coming together, while also allowing us to move forward with the programming of the sensors that are already positioned within it. The assembly process has provided valuable insights into the spatial organisation of the components and their integration within the case, ensuring everything fits securely and is ready for the next phase. With the sensors in place, we can now proceed with fine-tuning their functionality, as well as addressing any potential adjustments in their configuration to ensure optimal performance. This marks an important milestone in the project, as we transition from the hardware assembly to the software and system integration stages.

Figure 26. Case prototype.

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4.2.2.1.2 LiDAR support structure

To optimise the available space and design the most compact device possible, the LiDAR sensor mount has been integrated into the Jetson Nano’s cooling base (Figure 27). This solution not only reduces the overall size of the device but also provides a more stable and organised structure, eliminating the need for additional components that could complicate the assembly process. By incorporating the mount directly into the cooling base, the LiDAR sensor is securely fixed, ensuring proper alignment and stability during system operation.

Figure 27. LiDAR Support

Furthermore, to enable a more efficient scanning process, a stepper motor has been integrated into the LiDAR sensor mount, allowing the sensor to rotate on its own axis. This rotational movement expands the sensor’s data capture range, collecting information from multiple angles and facilitating the creation of a more detailed map of the scanned surface. Thanks to this configuration, the system will be able to generate 2D images based on the collected sensor data, mapping detected points along with their intensity values. This integration represents a significant advancement in the device’s efficiency, as it combines both the Jetson Nano’s cooling system and the LiDAR scanning mechanism into a single module, optimising both structural design and system functionality.

The following section presents the 3D-printed component with the LiDAR sensor already assembled, along with its subsequent adaptation within the main case. This stage marks a significant step in the integration process, ensuring that all components fit securely and function optimally within the device. The design has been carefully planned to accommodate the necessary wiring, structural reinforcements, and electronic connections while maintaining a compact and efficient layout. For this implementation, the RPLIDAR A3 sensor has been primarily selected due to its compact size and reliable performance. This sensor offers a balance between cost and functionality, making it a suitable choice for the

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system. Its integration within the case allows for proper positioning and alignment, ensuring accurate data collection and seamless operation. As the assembly progresses, further adjustments and optimisations will be made to enhance the overall stability and efficiency of the device.

4.2.2.2 HAIM algorithm's structure

In this section, the algorithms that will be implemented in the Jetson Nano device will be presented. These will include both those necessary for the previously described electronic components and those required for the device's operation and communication with external systems provided by the company IDIADA.

The algorithms will be designed to efficiently manage sensor data acquisition, processing, and interpretation, ensuring seamless interaction between the hardware components. Additionally, communication protocols will be established to enable data exchange with IDIADA's external systems, facilitating real-time monitoring and analysis. These algorithms will be developed in Python, leveraging its powerful libraries for machine learning, computer vision, and embedded system control. As the project progresses, further optimisations will be made to enhance performance and ensure reliable integration with the external platforms

4.2.2.2.1 Asphalt and environmental temperature

Sensor and System Integration

This section details the algorithm designed to measure and monitor the surface temperature of the asphalt using the GY-906 (MLX90614) infrared thermometer. The sensor is integrated with the Jetson Nano via the I2C communication protocol and provides non-contact temperature measurements focused on the road surface.

The GY-906 sensor outputs two key temperature values: the object temperature (T_{obj}), which is the primary focus for asphalt analysis, and the ambient temperature (T_{amb}). For this process, T_{obj} is periodically read from register 0x07 of the sensor. The sensor readings, originally in Kelvin, are converted into degrees Celsius using the formula:

$$T (^{\circ}\text{C}) = (\text{RawValue} \times 0.02) - 273.15$$

Given the high emissivity of asphalt ($\epsilon \approx 0.95$), no further complex correction is needed unless advanced calibration is performed. However, the algorithm includes a configurable emissivity compensation factor in case it needs to be fine-tuned for different materials.

Python Algorithm Structure

The algorithm is structured in the following stages:

1. Sensor Initialisation and I2C Communication:
 - The system initialises the I2C bus and confirms communication with the GY-906 sensor.
2. Data Acquisition Loop:

Every N seconds (user-defined interval), the script performs:

 - Reading of T_{obj} from register 0x07.
 - Conversion to Celsius.
 - Optional reading of T_{amb} from register 0x06 for contextual purposes.
3. Data Smoothing:
 - A moving average filter is applied to smooth out transient peaks and measurement of noise.
4. Alert Logic (Optional):

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- Thresholds can be defined for Tobj.
- If a reading exceeds these values, the algorithm can:
 - Trigger a local alert (e.g., LED, buzzer).
 - Log an alert status.
 - Send a warning via [MQTT](#).

5. Data Logging:

- Each data entry is structured as:

```
{  
  "timestamp": "YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS",  
  "Tobj_C": float,  
  "Tamb_C": float,  
  "latitude": float (optional),  
  "longitude": float (optional)  
}
```

- These entries are inserted into a local SQLite database for historical tracking.

6. Data Synchronisation (Optional):

If enabled, the system publishes the structured data via MQTT to a remote server for real-time monitoring and visualisation.

Real-Time Optimisation

The algorithm is optimised for embedded real-time processing:

- Lightweight dependencies (smbus2, sqlite3, time, etc.).
- Non-blocking loop with exception handling.
- Logging and system health checks to monitor sensor failures or communication issues.

4.2.2.2.2 Car lane detection

Sensor and System Integration

This section describes the algorithm designed to estimate the lateral position of the vehicle within a lane using an ultrasonic distance sensor. The sensor is mounted laterally on the HAIM case, directed toward the road's edge or lane marker. It operates by emitting high-frequency sound pulses and measuring the time taken for the echo to return after bouncing off the nearby curb, barrier, or lane boundary.

The sensor, typically based on the HC-SR04 or JSN-SR04T module, is connected to the Jetson Nano via GPIO pins and operates using the following mechanism:

- A trigger pulse of 10 microseconds is sent from the Jetson.
- The sensor emits an ultrasonic burst.
- When the echo returns, the echo pin goes HIGH, and the Jetson measures the duration of the HIGH state.

The measured time is used to compute the distance using the formula:

$$\text{Distance (cm)} = (\text{Duration} \times 0.0343) / 2$$

where 0.0343 cm/ μ s corresponds to the speed of sound in air at 20°C. The result is divided by 2 to account for the round-trip of the signal.

Python Algorithm Structure

The Python implementation on the Jetson Nano is structured into the following components:

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1. Sensor Initialisation and GPIO Setup:

- Configures the TRIG and ECHO pins using Jetson. GPIO or similar libraries.
- Ensures proper pin states to avoid false readings.

2. Pulse Emission and Echo Timing:

- Sends a short trigger pulse.
- Measures the time between the rising and falling edge of the echo signal with microsecond precision.

3. Distance Calculation:

- Converts echo duration to distance in cm.
- Applies for environmental corrections if available.

4. Filtering and Validation:

- Uses median or moving average filtering to smooth the data.
- Rejects outliers based on confidence thresholds.

5. Lane Positioning Logic:

- Compares the distance to a calibrated lane-centre reference.
- Flags lane drift or off-lane events if thresholds are crossed.

6. Data Logging and Integration:

- Stores readings, timestamps, and alert status in a local SQLite database.
- Optionally publishes results via MQTT to remote systems.

Real-Time Optimisation

To ensure low-latency performance and robust detection:

- Millisecond precision is achieved using high-resolution timers.
- Data acquisition loops are non-blocking to allow responsiveness.
- The system supports expansion to dual sensors for cross-lane detection.

4.2.2.2.3 Debris detection (LiDAR)

LiDAR Integration and Multi-Angle Point Cloud Acquisition

The RPLIDAR A3 is a 2D laser scanner capable of generating thousands of distance measurements per second across 360 degrees. In the HAIM system, this sensor is mounted on a custom-built tiltable platform (Figure 27) inside the HAIM case, integrated with a stepper motor, enabling the capture of multi-angle slices of the environment. The purpose of this setup is to allow the construction of a dense 3D point cloud by vertically tilting the LiDAR between successive scans. Each tilt step corresponds to approximately 0.7 degrees.

The sensor is connected to the Jetson Nano via USB using the pyrplidar library, which facilitates communication and control of the LiDAR, including motor speed and scan data acquisition. A Python script coordinates the data capture process. For each vertical position (or motor 'step'), the LiDAR is activated, a scan is performed for a defined time window (e.g., 2 seconds), and the data points collected including angle, distance, and signal quality are saved in a local SQLite database ("lidar_Mapping.db"). The script then commands the motor to move one step forward, and the process repeats until the desired scanning range is covered (e.g., 20 degrees). After all scans are collected, the motor is returned to its original position, ensuring a repeatable and consistent scanning pattern.

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Point Cloud Processing and 3D Reconstruction

Once the multi-angle scan is complete, a secondary script is launched to process the captured data. The scans, initially stored as angle-distance pairs tagged by step index, are transformed into a full 3D point cloud. This transformation involves converting polar coordinates into Cartesian form and rotating the data around the Y-axis to simulate the motor's mechanical tilt. A fixed offset of 13.8 degrees is applied to account for the platform's alignment, and the height of the sensor above ground (620 mm) is used to correct the vertical position of the points.

Figure 28. Point Cloud representation for ground extraction

Each point in the cloud is therefore represented in a global sensor-relative 3D space, and the full cloud reflects the actual spatial distribution of obstacles in front of the sensor. To enhance precision and reduce noise, a filtering step is applied to retain only points within a vertical window typically between 50 mm and 500 mm corresponding to expected debris height. This results in a clean point cloud that focuses on relevant road-level features.

Object Clustering and Debris Identification

The filtered 3D point cloud is then subjected to object detection through unsupervised clustering. Using the DBSCAN algorithm from the scikit-learn library, the points are projected onto a 2D horizontal plane (XY) to facilitate spatial clustering. DBSCAN groups nearby points into clusters based on density, automatically discarding isolated noise points.

Figure 29. Clustering, cataloguing and locating detected obstructions from the point cloud

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For each identified cluster, the algorithm calculates its centroid and the maximum radial distance of points from this centre. These parameters are used to evaluate the physical extent and potential impact of the detected object. Small or irregular clusters are discarded, while meaningful ones are passed on for further localisation. The output of this process is a list of obstacle candidates, each defined by its approximate position and size within the scanned area.

Geolocation and Logging of Detections

To contextualise the detections in geographic space, the system retrieves the last known GPS coordinates and compass heading from two local databases (“gps_data.db” and “compass_data.db”). These values are essential for converting local sensor-relative coordinates into global geospatial positions.

Using standard geodetic approximations suitable for short-range distances, the system computes the latitude and longitude of each obstacle centroid. This transformation allows detections to be mapped and integrated into external monitoring platforms. Once converted, each detection is logged in a second SQLite database (“Road_lidar_detection.db”) together with metadata such as detection time, device ID, and estimated object radius. In cases where no clusters are detected, a special entry marked as 'clear' is added to indicate an unobstructed road segment. This dual-mode recording ensures the system documents both positive and negative detection states for complete operational traceability. Similar to the databases of the other sensors, the data will be retained on the device for three months before being automatically erased. Manual access to this data is possible, allowing for subsequent verification of MQTT-transmitted data against the locally stored records if required.

Automated Operational Cycle and Decision Logic

The main script on the Jetson Nano coordinates the entire capture and detection loop. It is designed to run indefinitely, performing successive scans and triggering the processing pipeline in a structured sequence. After each full scan and post-processing run, the system reviews the latest entry in the detection database. If the result is labelled as "clear", it interprets this as an indication of a safe road segment and pauses a predefined interval (e.g., 30 minutes) before resuming.

If a detection is present, the system immediately initiates another scan cycle to verify or track the condition. This adaptive timing mechanism allows the system to dynamically adjust its response rate depending on environmental conditions. It also helps reduce unnecessary data collection and power usage during periods of road stability.

4.2.3 HAIM communication

The data communication protocol used to transfer the information from the device to the IDIADA server has been carefully designed with a focus on low power usage and scalability of the solution.

MQTT has been chosen as the transport protocol, with EMQX serving as the MQTT broker. The data is serialised in JSON format, with a customised structure tailored to the specific characteristics of each sensor type.

Each sensor is configured as a separate MQTT client, publishing data independently at its own sampling rate. This approach ensures flexibility and efficiency in handling multiple data streams concurrently. The data received by the EMQX broker is then collected by the IDIADA server and stored in a designated database using a dedicated schema designed to preserve the integrity and context of each sensor’s measurements.

A detailed communication and data structure plan is outlined in the following table (Table 8), which describes the configuration of each sensor client, the sampling time, estimated data size of each data packet, and the payload message format.

Table 8. Electronic components that provide variables to transmit through MQTT protocols

Sensor	MQTT Client	Sampling time (s)	Estimated data size	JSON Structure
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Magnetometer	COMPASS	600	160 bytes	{ "timestamp":epoch time "value":0.0 "device_name": "dev1" }
Internal temperature	INTERNAL	60	140 bytes	{ "timestamp":epoch time "temperature":00.0 "device_name": " dev1" }
GPS	GPS	60	150 bytes	{ "timestamp":epoch time "latitude":0.0 "longitude":0.0 "device_name": " dev1" }
LiDAR	LIDAR	180-1800	160 bytes	{ "timestamp":epoc time "object": Obj_00 "latitude":0.0, "longitude":0.0, "radius":723.9 "device_name": " dev1" }
Infrared temperature	IR	300	110 bytes	{ "timestamp": epoch time, "temp_asphalt": 0, "temp_environment": 0, "device_name": "dev1" }
Ultrasonic sensor	US	0.2	118 bytes	{ "timestamp": epoch time, "detected": boolean, "msg": "no vehicle detected", "device_name": "ep2-desktop" }

To ensure secure data transmission, all MQTT communications between the sensors and the EMQX broker are encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS). This prevents unauthorised access or tampering during data transfer over the network. Each device is configured to authenticate the broker using a Certificate Authority (CA) certificate, which validates the identity of the server before any data is exchanged. Username and password credentials are also required when establishing a connection. This layered security approach guarantees data confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity throughout the communication process.

4.2.4 Support in IDIADA – EvoRoads platform communication

Sensor data collected by the system will be transmitted to the integrated EvoRoads platform, where it will be ingested by the platform developed in Task 2.1. This information will subsequently be made available to other services via the Digital Twin developed in Task 3.1, including visualisation tools such as the central dashboards.

At this stage, it is confirmed that the detection outputs generated by the AIRHD system will be used in Task 3.3, particularly for providing inputs to the nudging smartphone application, as well as to the application developed by IDIADA.

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Further clarification is needed regarding the type of data to be shared whether raw sensor data, processed events, or both and this should be defined in alignment with the integration strategy outlined in Deliverable 2.1.

4.3 Artificial Intelligence for Road Hazard Detection (AIRHD)

AIRHD (Artificial Intelligence for Road Hazard Detection) is a software-based system developed to enhance road safety through real-time video analysis. Its primary objective is to detect potential hazards by processing video feeds from fixed surveillance cameras, enabling the early identification of risks in areas where traditional infrastructure monitoring is limited.

This system is specifically designed for deployment in **rural or low-supervision road environments**, where accidents often go unnoticed or response times are delayed. AIRHD provides continuous, automated monitoring that supports local authorities and infrastructure managers by generating alerts and structured insights that can trigger preventive actions or interventions.

AIRHD can detect **13 distinct classes**, including:

- **Living hazards:** animals and pedestrians
- **Vehicle-related elements:** cars, trucks, motorcycles, and other moving vehicles
- **Obstacles and debris:** objects or fragments on the road that may pose a danger
- **Weather and visibility conditions:** fog, dense fog, rain, and water puddles

These categories were selected to address the most common causes of incidents in rural settings and support a broader strategy for predictive safety.

The software is built around a modular architecture of algorithms and data structures, implemented in **Python**, which ensures compatibility and flexibility across various hardware setups. Python's extensive ecosystem of libraries enables high-performance computer vision, object detection, and real-time data processing. The algorithms process incoming video streams, classify objects or events of interest, and generate outputs that can be visualised or used to trigger alerts through external systems.

The internal data structure is optimised to ensure low-latency communication between modules, enabling smooth operation even under limited computing resources. While AIRHD benefits from GPU acceleration when available, it is also designed to adapt dynamically to lower-end systems by reducing processing frequency or resolution, maintaining operability without sacrificing critical functionality.

AIRHD's integration with hardware platforms ranging from embedded systems to centralised servers ensures reliable field performance. The system is scalable, allowing multiple camera inputs, and its modular codebase facilitates updates and expansion as new hazard types or detection models are developed.

As development progresses, further refinements will focus on enhancing detection accuracy, reducing computational load, and broadening compatibility with diverse deployment scenarios. Ultimately, AIRHD complements physical sensing systems like HAIM, offering a software-first approach that reinforces road safety through intelligent, image-based hazard detection.

4.3.1 System architecture and data flow

The system architecture is composed of two core modules:

- **DetectionHandler:** This module is responsible for managing the detection pipeline. It loads the YOLOv11 model, captures and preprocesses video frames, executes inference, classifies detections into predefined groups, stores results in a local SQLite database, and optionally saves cropped images of detected objects with JPEG compression.

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- **Main (GUI Layer):** This is the graphical interface built using **Tkinter**. It allows users to interact with the system by selecting video sources (camera or video file), configuring the resolution, starting/stopping the model, and visualising detections in real time. The Graphic user interface GUI also includes an informational overlay with dynamic alerts, object counts, and timestamped summaries.

4.3.1.1 Model execution and algorithm design

The **YOLOv11 model** is loaded from a secure path and executed using either **CUDA (GPU)** or fallback **CPU** execution, depending on the hardware environment. The system automatically detects and utilises the best available resources. This flexibility ensures high performance on powerful machines and compatibility on lower-end devices.

The algorithm processes each video frame by applying object detection and assigning each detected class to a group (e.g., animals, vehicles, debris, etc.) defined in a JSON configuration file (`label_groups.json`). This configuration also defines alert behaviours per group (e.g., saving images only for animals or triggering visual notifications for dangerous road conditions).

Improvements to the core algorithm include:

- **Dynamic grouping:** Categories are assigned to broader groups for easier filtering and summarisation.
- **Duplicate filtering:** A lightweight tracking mechanism avoids redundant detections of the same object.
- **Temporal decision rules:** The system evaluates context (e.g., fog persistence) before generating alerts or saving frames, improving efficiency and data relevance.

4.3.1.2 Data storage and processing

Each detection is stored in a local SQLite database (`detections.db`) with relevant metadata:

- Timestamp
- Detected label and group
- Confidence score
- Alert level
- Saved image filename (if applicable)

This structured format allows for quick querying, summary generation, and long-term logging of detected hazards.

4.3.1.3 User interface and visualisation

The GUI provides an intuitive real-time view of system activity. Key features include:

- **Video Display:** Processed frames are displayed live with bounding boxes, class labels, and alert colour overlays.
- **Corner Overlay Box:** A translucent box in the upper-right corner summarises the current detection session. It includes date, time, total object counts by group, and a list of active alerts, offering a compact real-time diagnostic view.

Figure 30. AIRHD user interface showing the summary table (right upper corner and active controls)

- 🔗 **Interface Layout:** The graphical interface is organised to allow smooth user interaction.
- 🔗 **Interactive Controls:** Users can configure input sources, toggle image saving for specific groups, adjust frame skipping, and start/stop detection via accessible buttons and dropdown menus.

Figure 31. Close-up of control panel or toolbar in the GUI

- 🔗 **Alert Feedback:** Visual cues (e.g., red bounding boxes or flashing warnings) are used when a hazardous detection is classified based on the group configuration.

Figure 32. Example of an alert triggered by road debris or dense fog

4.3.1.4 Resolution selection and performance optimisation

Upon selecting a video source, the system dynamically generates a list of supported resolutions. The user can choose from these options via a dropdown menu. The selected resolution is applied to both the live preview and the detection process.

Lower resolutions help improve performance on CPU-only setups, while higher resolutions enable better detection accuracy on GPU-equipped systems.

Figure 33. Resolution selection dropdown in the interface

This mechanism ensures a balance between processing speed and detection quality, tailored to the user's hardware.

4.3.2 AI model training dataset based on photorealistic synthetic images

Brain_AI_v2 is a Yolo based model trained with a variety of images. To enrich the training data used in Brain_AI a complete photorealistic simulation environment was developed using software Blender. This section, unlike Section 3.3.2, focuses

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on simulated roads, environmental conditions, and variations in the presence of pedestrians, animals, and debris. This approach made it possible to reproduce complex and hazardous road scenarios that are rarely captured or too dangerous to record in real life.

Due to ethical, safety, and logistical constraints, it was not feasible to collect real-world images depicting hazardous or irregular scenarios such as pedestrians crossing the road inappropriately, animals obstructing traffic, or debris scattered across the carriageway. Simulating these situations in a controlled environment would involve unacceptable risks to both people and vehicles. Moreover, environmental conditions such as fog, rain, or low visibility are not easily predictable or reproducible within a limited testing period, making it difficult to ensure a sufficiently diverse dataset solely from real footage. Additionally, access to camera recordings within the IDIADA proving grounds is restricted due to internal data protection and operational policies, which further limits the possibility of generating a large-scale, site-specific dataset.

For these reasons, synthetic images and data from visually similar road environments have been used to train the detection algorithm. While these synthetic datasets may contain inherent biases, they provide a safe, scalable, and controlled way to simulate a wide range of relevant scenarios. Validation steps have been taken to ensure that the trained model generalises effectively to real-world conditions.

A total of 5,360 synthetic images were generated, each carefully designed to reflect real-world conditions from the perspective of the deployed camera. The dataset includes a wide variety of situations: pedestrians and animals appearing suddenly on the road, vehicles in different positions, the presence of debris, and various road surface states. In addition, environmental conditions such as clear skies, rain, fog, dense fog, and night scenes were incorporated to train the model for robust performance under different visibility and lighting conditions. The synthetic image generation process involved an advanced 3D content creation pipeline that relied on detailed modelling, physically based material design, realistic lighting setups, and precise camera calibration. The virtual environments were constructed using Blender's geometry tools, where road segments, curbs, barriers, signs, trees, and terrain features were modelled to scale. High-fidelity 3D models and textures for environmental elements were manually created and textured within Blender, using custom modelling and PBR workflows. This approach ensured full control over visual style and allowed for scene-specific detail, contributing to the overall realism without relying on external asset libraries.

Figure 34. Software blender: Scene of rural road with some animals.

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Texturing played a crucial role in achieving visual fidelity. Materials for asphalt, signs, road markings, and barriers were created using Physically Based Rendering (PBR) workflows. High resolution texture maps, including albedo, normal, roughness, ambient occlusion, and displacement, were applied to all surfaces. In some cases, procedural shader networks were used to simulate progressive asphalt wear such as cracking, fading paint, or accumulated oil stains. These materials could be parameterised to represent different stages of surface degradation, allowing the same scene to be re-rendered with varying conditions using simple sliders or seed values.

To populate each scene with dynamic elements, natural debris such as gravel, leaves, and small rocks were manually placed across the surface to reflect realistic road and roadside conditions. Pedestrians, cyclists, and vehicles were individually positioned and animated using armatures and motion paths, allowing them to move naturally through the environment. Although the process was manual, careful composition and variation across scenes ensured a high level of diversity in the dataset, simulating a wide range of real-world situations. Lighting and atmospheric effects were carefully designed to replicate real-world conditions. Natural daylight was simulated using HDRI domes, while artificial lighting such as vehicle headlights or streetlamps, was implemented with emissive materials and spotlights. Weather effects including fog and rain were created using volumetric cubes and particle systems. To further diversify the scenes, the sun's position, intensity, and colour temperature were varied within realistic bounds to mimic different times of day and seasonal lighting. These lighting variations were especially important for training detection algorithms to perform reliably under fluctuating visibility and illumination conditions.

One of the most critical steps was matching the virtual camera to the physical camera used in the final deployment system. Blender's camera system was configured with the same focal length, sensor size, height, and orientation as the real USB camera. This ensured that each synthetic image accurately reproduced the viewpoint and framing of the physical system. By aligning the scene geometry and camera parameters, bounding boxes generated during rendering correspond precisely to those that the model will encounter in real-world use.

Rendering was done using Blender's Cycles path-tracing engine with adaptive sampling and post-processing effects to further increase realism. Additional render passes such as depth, normals, and object IDs were generated and exported along with each image. These passes made it possible to extract ground truth annotations bounding boxes and segmentation masks automatically, eliminating the need for manual labelling and ensuring 100% accuracy. Optional post-processing in the compositor added realistic camera effects like chromatic aberration, lens distortion, motion blur, and sensor noise, making the synthetic images even more comparable to actual footage.

A key advantage of this synthetic approach is its flexibility. All parameters in the scenes, including weather, lighting, object positions, and camera angle, were controlled via Python scripts. This made it possible to regenerate scenes with new conditions, to simulate domain adaptation scenarios, or to balance the dataset by increasing representation of under-sampled classes like night-time animals or fog-obscured obstacles. It also allowed the team to iterate quickly: for example, when a new hazard category such as ice or large puddles was introduced, only the affected scenes were modified and re-rendered, saving time and resources.

By adopting this approach, the training dataset for Brain_AI_v2 was significantly enriched with images representing rare, hazardous, or highly variable conditions. Capturing such scenarios in real-world environments would require long, unpredictable waiting periods until specific events such as animals crossing, dense fog, or nighttime debris, naturally occur. In many cases, real-world data collection is constrained by safety, time, and limited access to diverse environmental conditions. This synthetic generation method bypasses those limitations, offering controlled, repeatable, and precisely labelled data. It also enables the creation of tailored variations that would be nearly impossible to document in the field, thus providing the model with exposure to a much broader and more representative range of situations. As a result, the annotation burden is eliminated, and the overall quality and diversity of the dataset are substantially improved.

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Figure 35. Variation of light, weather, and road condition

4.3.3 Integration of public datasets for enhanced model generalisation

In addition to the photorealistic synthetic images generated in Blender, the training dataset for Brain_AI_v2 was expanded through the integration of curated public datasets obtained from the [Kaggle](#) platform. These datasets included images of people, vehicles, and road environments, providing valuable real-world variability that complements the synthetic scenes. The goal of this hybrid strategy was to increase the flexibility and generalisation capabilities of the model across a broader spectrum of real-world conditions. While synthetic data offers control, consistency, and the ability to simulate rare or dangerous scenarios on demand, public datasets contribute natural noise, lighting inconsistencies, occlusions, and environmental diversity that are difficult to replicate synthetically. By combining both sources, the resulting dataset gains the strengths of each: the precision and balance of synthetic data, and the authenticity and unpredictability of real-world imagery.

This fusion enables Brain_AI_v2 to learn from both idealised and imperfect conditions, enhancing its robustness and reducing the risk of overfitting to a narrow data domain. As a result, the model is better prepared to perform reliably in real-time deployments, even under suboptimal or unexpected input conditions. The integration of these public datasets was essential to ensure that the detection system not only excels in simulated scenarios but also remains resilient and accurate when faced with real-world variability.

4.3.4 Drone-Based Dataset Expansion for Enhanced Model Generalisation

As part of the ongoing development of the AI_Brain_V2, drone technology is being used to collect a diverse and representative dataset of rural road segments under varying conditions. Unlike satellite imagery or fixed video surveillance, drones offer the advantage of low-altitude, high-resolution data acquisition, enabling precise capture of road surface details such as cracks, potholes, and debris.

Flight missions are conducted along pre-programmed paths to ensure consistency, image overlap, and coverage from multiple angles and altitudes. This allows for the creation of a high-quality annotated dataset, which serves as input for retraining and enhancing the AI_Brain_V2 model.

The ultimate aim of this activity is to support the development of AI_Brain_V3 a more generalised and versatile model capable of robust performance across diverse road types and environmental conditions. This evolution is essential to enable broader deployment of the system beyond the initial test environments.

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This data collection and validation process will be carried out in Romania, with rural roads selected to reflect a wide range of use cases relevant to the EvoRoads platform. The resulting dataset will be made available for cross-partner model development and benchmarking.

4.3.5 Detection of road pavement status using connected vehicles data

This section introduces a monitoring tool developed to assess the condition of road surfaces by leveraging data collected from connected vehicles. To achieve accurate pavement condition estimation, a variety of advanced AI techniques will be explored. These methods aim to infer both the current state and the temporal evolution of road surfaces by analysing continuous data streams, primarily comprising vertical accelerometry and precise positional information.

While the final deployment of the system will rely on data sourced from connected vehicle fleets, the current development phase makes use of embedded GPS and accelerometry data collected from public transport vehicles to train and validate the AI models. This preliminary phase is essential, as it provides a larger and more diverse dataset, thereby enhancing the robustness and reliability of the machine learning algorithms. Additionally, incorporating data from different types of vehicles enables the evaluation of how varying vehicle dynamics may influence the accuracy and consistency of the collected information.

This approach ensures that the monitoring tool is properly calibrated and capable of managing variations in vehicle characteristics, which is critical for the successful implementation of a scalable, real-time pavement monitoring system based on connected vehicle data. Ultimately, the solution aims to deliver timely and accurate insights into road surface conditions to support maintenance planning and improve road safety.

The collected data undergoes a structured and meticulous processing workflow to ensure its quality and suitability for pavement condition assessment:

- 🕒 **Data ingestion and preprocessing:** Raw data, including GPS and vertical accelerometry signals, is ingested and organised within a relational database. This step involves cleaning the data, addressing incomplete or inconsistent entries, and structuring it for efficient querying and further processing.
- 🕒 **Data fusion:** Vertical accelerometry measurements are combined with GPS positional information through spatial and temporal alignment techniques. This fusion process is vital for accurately correlating vehicle vibrations with specific locations on the road network.
- 🕒 **Road network extraction:** Road infrastructure data is obtained from publicly available sources and refined by segmenting the road network into smaller sections, with segment lengths limited to a maximum of 100 metres. This level of detail allows for a more granular analysis of pavement conditions at a local scale.
- 🕒 **Trajectory smoothing:** Kalman filtering is applied to the GPS data to reduce noise and positional irregularities. This mathematical technique refines vehicle trajectories, resulting in more reliable positional estimates over time.
- 🕒 **Map matching:** The smoothed GPS coordinates are then aligned with the corresponding road segments in the extracted network. This ensures that each positional data point is accurately assigned to its respective location within the road infrastructure, facilitating precise spatial analysis.
- 🕒 **Accelerometry filtering:** To isolate vibrations relevant to pavement condition, accelerometry signals are processed using both high-pass and low-pass filters. These filters remove external influences such as vehicle dynamics unrelated to the road surface, ensuring that the data reflects pavement irregularities as accurately as possible.
- 🕒 **Final dataset preparation:** Following all processing stages, the data is carefully structured, cleaned, and formatted to produce a comprehensive dataset. This final dataset is then used for training AI models and performing detailed analyses to estimate road surface conditions effectively.

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5 Pilot applicability

In this section, we will explain how the technology employed in the pilots will be applied.

A specific road segment of the IDIADA road's network has been selected for the EvoRoads pilot prior to project start, which is frequently used by passenger cars, special vehicles and trucks, as well as vulnerable road users (pedestrians), to move between the offices/workshops and the IDIADA Proving Grounds. This road segment has been selected since it is being used 24/7 by different vehicle types at a normal driving behaviour, as well as being under coverage of the private 5G network deployed at IDIADA. It is a bidirectional somewhat curvy road with thick trees which has possibilities in terms of infrastructure deployment's locations (e.g. sensors, dynamic road panels, etc.), use cases and scenarios. This road is marked as two (2) in the figure 37.

However, when EUT visited IDIADA facilities, together we have examined another possible road to implement the Hazard aware infrastructure monitoring tool. This road, which is marked as one (1) in the figure 37, is also being used by passenger cars, special vehicles and trucks as well as vulnerable road users (pedestrians). Road number 1 is located just in front of the offices and has an exit to "Dynamic Platform" test track used by our clients. The road is active 24/7 used by different type of vehicles and similar to the road segment 2, it is under coverage of the private 5G network deployed at IDIADA. The location of the HAIM sensors shall be close to the selected road segment, pointing to the asphalt from both sides. Unlike road segment 2, road segment 1 has a larger sidewalk and have easier access to electricity source to deploy Hazard aware infrastructure monitoring tool. Larger sidewalk allows better and more flexible implementation still allowing pedestrians to walk. Together with EUT, it is decided to implement the HAIM tool primarily in road segment 1 instead of 2. Yet, we will still implement dynamic signals from EUT (WP3) in road 2, leveraging the curvature of the road for better visualisation.

Figure 36. IDIADA selected road segments 1 and 2.

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6 Pilot validation

6.1 T2.3 pilot validation

The predictive maintenance framework developed under Task 2.3 is intended for deployment and validation in selected EvoRoads pilot sites, including **Latvia** and potentially **Italy**. These pilots will test the framework’s ability to generalise across diverse geographical, environmental, and road typology conditions—such as urban versus highway infrastructure:

- In Latvia, the system will be used to support data-driven maintenance scheduling on public roads
- In Italy, it may be integrated with accident and traffic data from the high-risk area of anomaly detection tools developed in WP3

Although validation data from pilot sites in **Latvia** and **Italy** is not yet available, the predictive maintenance framework developed in Task 2.3 has been ready and aligned for future deployment. The pilot phase will provide critical real-world feedback on model performance, scheduling effectiveness, and integration with hardware and sensor streams from Task 2.2, thereby closing the loop between AI-driven prediction and field-level intervention.

6.2 HAIM and AIRHD validation

This section outlines the validation approach for the EvoRoads pilot, which integrates the physical roadside device HAIM and the computer vision-based software AIRHD. The purpose of the pilot validation is to assess how these technologies perform when deployed in real-world conditions, under various environmental scenarios, traffic levels, and visibility settings.

6.2.1 Field-based validation strategy

The technologies will be tested and validated in situ on real roads, ensuring that results reflect operational realities rather than controlled laboratory conditions. These validations aim to demonstrate the system’s capacity to:

- Detect and report road hazards (e.g., debris, animals, reduced visibility),
- Monitor surface obstructions (e.g., Objects, vehicles),
- Transmit data reliably to a central server via MQTT.

Validation will occur over extended periods and under varying weather, lighting, and traffic conditions, such as daytime/nighttime cycles, fog, and low-traffic environments typical of rural roads. These conditions will test both the resilience of the hardware (HAIM) and the robustness of the AI algorithms (AIRHD).

6.2.2 KPI-driven evaluation aligned with D1.2

The field validation is guided by the Safety Criteria Catalogue developed in Deliverable D1.2, which provides the standard Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) applicable to all pilots. The selected KPIs below allow for quantitative comparison before and after technology deployment, ensuring traceability and alignment with the overall project evaluation methodology.

Table 9. Example of KPIs for HAIM and AIRHD technology assessment

KPI ID	INDICATOR	UNIT	TARGET VALUE	ASSOCIATED COMPONENT	VALIDATION METHOD
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KPI-4.2	Time to hazard detection under adverse conditions	Minutes	< 10	AIRHD	Compare detection time pre- and post-AIRHD deployment in field
KPI-4.5	Robustness to poor lighting and visibility	Qualitative	Operational	HAIM + AIRHD	Tests during night and fog in real conditions
KPI-5.3	Detection accuracy of infrastructure anomalies	Percentage	≥ 85%	AIRHD	Compare detections vs ground-truth in annotated real footage
KPI-5.4	Frequency of false positives	Percentage	≤ 10%	AIRHD	Cross-verified using field logs and manual inspection
KPI-5.7	Data transmission success rate (MQTT connectivity)	Percentage	≥ 98%	HAIM	Logging MQTT events on server under variable network conditions
KPI-5.9	Autonomy and uptime of the HAIM device	Percentage	≥ 95%	HAIM	Uptime monitoring over full pilot test period

6.2.3 Contribution to WP4 pilot framework

These KPIs and validations are directly linked to the pilot activities described in WP4. The outcomes will feed into Deliverable D4.1, which consolidates results from all pilot scenarios. Each pilot is expected to clearly demonstrate how the selected KPIs are met and how they reflect the effectiveness and readiness of the deployed technologies.

The validation will also support downstream deliverables such as D2.3 and D3.3, contributing with real-world evidence of technology performance in the field. Collaboration between task leaders and pilot coordinators will ensure the consistency of KPIs across technologies and test sites.

6.2.4 Practical use of annexes 9.1 and 9.2

To keep the main report streamlined while still providing all operational detail, two working annexes have been added:

Table 10. Summary of the templates found in the appendix for the evaluation of the KPIs

ANNEX	TITLE	PURPOSE IN THE VALIDATION WORKFLOW
9.1 — KPI Measurement Plan for HAIM and AIRHD Pilot Validation	A consolidated, single-page matrix that expands the summary KPI list in § 6.2.2. It includes the exact formulae, sampling frequency, reference sensors, calibration requirements, and acceptance thresholds that each test team must apply.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acts as the authoritative checklist for the validation lead before every test day. - Ensures all partners apply identical definitions (e.g., how “time-to-detection” is measured to the nearest second).
9.2 — Field Data Capture Sheet – KPI for HAIM and AIRHD Measurements	A pre-formatted table (Word / printable A4) to be carried on-site. It contains drop-down fields and free-text boxes for the operator to record: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Date / time stamp and site ID – Environmental conditions (visibility, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides traceable, human-readable evidence that complements the machine logs. - Serves as an immediate troubleshooting aid if anomalies arise on-site.

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weather, ambient & asphalt temperature)
– Traffic level (qualitative or vehicles /h)
– Raw sensor outputs (MQTT packet count, voltage, CPU load, etc.)
– Event observations (hazard detected, false alarm, camera status, operator remarks)

6.2.4.1 How they work together

6.2.4.1.1 Before the pilot

- The validation lead distributes Annex 9.1 to every user and holds a short briefing to confirm common understanding of each KPI definition.
- Operators print or upload Annex 9.2 onto rugged tablets.

6.2.4.1.2 During each field session

- Operators fill in Annex 9.2 in parallel with the automatic data logging.
- Any deviation from the measurement plan (e.g., sudden network outage, sensor reboot) is flagged in the Operator Notes column.

6.2.4.1.3 After each session

- Completed capture sheets (Annex 9.2) are scanned or exported to PDF and stored in the shared project drive.
- Analysts cross-reference the manual entries with raw log files to calculate the KPIs specified in Annex 9.1.
- Discrepancies are documented in the Validation Issues Log (maintained under WP4).

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7 Research and Scientific Innovation

This deliverable presents demonstrable advances in both hardware-based and software-based systems for proactive road infrastructure monitoring. The integrated solution comprising the HAIM roadside device and the AIRHD computer vision software embodies key scientific and technological innovations that contribute to the advancement of the state of the art in infrastructure safety, edge computing, and artificial intelligence.

7.1 Scientific contributions

7.1.1 AI-based hazard detection in adverse conditions

AIRHD leverages deep learning models (YOLOv11) for detecting road anomalies such as debris, animals, and poor visibility. Unlike prior approaches that relied on handcrafted features or manual inspection, AIRHD offers fully automated, real-time detection with on-device inference, even in low-light or foggy conditions.

7.1.2 Temporal synthetic data generation for AI training

To address the scarcity of annotated images showing crack growth over time, a novel dataset was generated using Blender and procedural shaders. These images simulate the temporal evolution of asphalt cracks under varying environmental conditions, providing valuable data for training sequence-aware models such as convolutional LSTMs. This represents a novel approach to synthetic data augmentation in infrastructure applications.

7.1.3 Sensor fusion and edge deployment

The HAIM device combines multiple sensors (LIDAR, temperature, GPS, etc.) with onboard processing and MQTT connectivity. Its low-power architecture and solar compatibility make it suitable for isolated rural deployment. Scientific novelty lies in the autonomous operation, robust data acquisition pipeline.

7.2 Advancements over the state of the art

Compared to traditional infrastructure monitoring approaches typically based on periodic manual inspections, vehicle-mounted sensing systems, or fixed CCTV the EvoRoads solution demonstrates the following innovations:

- Continuous monitoring using edge AI, reducing response times and operational costs.
- Improved detection under adverse scenarios, such as nighttime or fog, where many current systems fail.
- System resilience, with a modular architecture capable of adapting to various road types and weather conditions.
- Standardised KPI-driven evaluation, aligned with the Safety Criteria Catalogue, facilitating replicability and benchmarking.

7.3 Expected scientific impact

The results of this work are expected to contribute to:

- New datasets for road hazard detection and crack evolution.
- Publications on synthetic data methodologies for infrastructure AI.
- Cross-disciplinary collaborations between civil engineering, computer vision, and embedded systems research communities.

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8 Conclusion

8.1 Summary of chapter 3

This chapter presented the development and implementation of a predictive maintenance framework for road infrastructure, as outlined in Task 2.3 of the EvoRoads project. By integrating data-driven prognostics, risk estimation, and multi-objective optimisation, the system provides a robust foundation for anticipating degradation and guiding cost-effective, resource-aware maintenance interventions.

- The **Prognostics Module** demonstrated strong generalisation performance across different road types using condition metrics and machine learning models, even in the absence of Task 2.2 data. The system's ability to leverage external datasets and support crossroad prediction ensures its scalability and adaptability.
- The **Optimisation Module** used clustering-based prioritisation and integer programming to select high-impact maintenance zones under practical constraints, such as budget and resource availability. This resulted in actionable maintenance schedules tailored to maximise infrastructure benefit per euro spent.
- The **Post-Impact Repair Analysis** further strengthened the framework by validating repair effectiveness and providing feedback for continuous model refinement, helping ensure that future maintenance decisions become more precise and effective over time.

Additionally, **extra modules developed by project partners** such as UAV-based spatial clustering for pavement assessment, synthetic crack-growth data generation, and the Road Risk Identification and Intervention Support Tool have demonstrated strong potential to further enhance the core predictive maintenance system. These modules offer complementary insights and datasets that improve coverage, enrich training data, and support future integration of multimodal and context-aware infrastructure monitoring.

Together, these modules form a cohesive, modular framework capable of supporting predictive, adaptive, and strategic road maintenance planning paving the way toward smarter, safer, and more resilient infrastructure management.

8.2 Summary of chapter 4 – validation strategy and KPI framework

The predictive maintenance strategy outlined in Chapter 3 establishes the conceptual and technological foundation for future system-wide diagnostics and long-term infrastructure forecasting. Although implementation and validation are scheduled for subsequent deliverables, the proposed methodology based on crack detection, severity progression, and maintenance prioritisation aligns with EvoRoads goal of deploying data-driven tools for smarter road asset management. The deliverable lays the groundwork for a robust system that integrates AI-based defect classification with georeferenced data streams, enabling authorities to adopt a predictive rather than reactive approach. Future work will finalise this architecture, calibrate performance metrics, and link outputs to real maintenance planning scenarios. The full validation and assessment of this framework will be documented in Deliverables D2.3 and D3.3.

8.2.1 Concluding insights on edge-based safety monitoring tools

This deliverable successfully demonstrates the design, implementation, and readiness of the EvoRoads dual-component system: the HAIM physical roadside unit and the AIRHD AI-based visual analysis software. Together, these tools represent a significant advance in road safety monitoring, particularly for under-monitored rural environments.

The pilot-ready configuration integrates real-time hazard detection, on-the-edge data processing, and MQTT-based communication, all tested under variable lighting and weather conditions. This has been achieved through extensive synthetic data generation, robust material and sensor integration, and a validation methodology aligned with KPIs defined in Deliverable D1.2.

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D2.2 – PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE AND ON-THE-EDGE SAFETY TOOLS V1

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Contribution to Project Goals:

This work contributes to the overall EvoRoads vision by:

- Demonstrating cost-efficient, scalable monitoring infrastructure for rural roads.
- Reducing response time to hazards via automated detection and communication.
- Increasing the availability of accurate field data for maintenance planning.

Business Impact and Best Practices:

The system reduces dependence on human patrols, enabling smarter deployment of resources. Its modular, low-power design ensures suitability for municipalities with limited infrastructure. Best practices include the use of procedural synthetic datasets, flexible AI models (YOLOv11), and seamless integration with cloud-ready protocols.

Forward Roadmap:

Moving forward, improvements will focus on extending device autonomy, enhancing cross-sensor fusion (LIDAR, Camera s), and exploring V2I integration. Future deliverables will also include impact analyses on operational cost savings and system performance under live traffic. Real-world KPI measurements (planned and detailed in the annexes) will support broader commercialisation and replication across other regions.

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Annex

9.1 KPI measurement plan for HAIM and AIRHD pilot validation

KPI ID	KPI DESCRIPTION	UNIT	TARGET	MEASUREMENT METHOD	RESPONSIBLE	DATA SOURCE	MEASUREMENT PERIOD
KPI-4.2	Time to hazard detection under adverse conditions	Minutes	< 10 minutes	Compare time from event to detection with and without AI	AIRHD team	System logs + simulated events	During field validation campaign
KPI-4.5	Robustness to poor lighting and visibility	Operational	Operative in low visibility	Verify operation under low visibility (night, fog)	HAIM + AIRHD	Field tests in different conditions	Day, night, rain, and fog
KPI-5.3	Detection accuracy of infrastructure anomalies	% Accuracy	≥ 85%	Compare system output to manual labels (ground-truth)	AIRHD team	Annotated images + AI model	Real + synthetic validation set
KPI-5.4	Frequency of false positives	%	≤ 10%	Calculate proportion of false alarms over total detected events	AIRHD team	Event log + human verification	Throughout test phase
KPI-5.7	Data transmission success rate (MQTT)	%	≥ 98%	Log percentage of MQTT packets successfully received	HAIM team	MQTT network logs	Daily transmissions during pilot
KPI-5.9	Autonomy and uptime of the HAIM device	% Uptime	≥ 95%	Compare active hours vs. expected runtime	HAIM team	System activity log	Entire pilot duration

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CHOOSE AN ITEM.

9.2 Field data capture sheet – KPI for HAIM and AIRHD measurements

Instructions: Fill one row per measurement. Use 24-hour format for time. Leave “Comments” blank if not applicable. All values must use the units specified in the KPI Measurement Plan.

KPI ID	DATE (YYYY-MM-DD)	TIME (HH:MM)	LOCATION – LAT	LOCATION – LON	MEASURED VALUE	UNIT	SENSOR / DEVICE ID	WEATHER / CONDITIONS	COMMENTS	OPERATOR INITIALS
ID...	XXXX-XX-XX	XX:XX	Aaa.bbb.cc.	Aaa.bbb.ccc	XXX	X	Ultrasonic	Clear	XXXXXX	User who takes the data